

LOW-TECH PROCESS-BASED RESTORATION DESIGN AND MONITORING PROTOCOL

STANDARD METHODS FOR DEVELOPING PROJECT DESIGNS AND MONITORING
RIVERSCAPE HEALTH

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This protocol is the result of decades of work by the authors, their collaborators, and countless others before them. The protocol grew out of efforts to simplify and extend riverscape monitoring methods that were primarily focused on instream channel habitats and that used high resolution topographic survey methods in the Columbia Habitat Monitoring Program (CHaMP -<https://www.streamnet.org/home/data-maps/champ/>) and the Integrated Status and Effectiveness Monitoring Program (ISEMP - <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/30831>). Earlier versions of “rapid field protocols” and “CHaMP-light” provided the early testing and foundation for these protocols. The protocol has benefitted from the input of numerous researchers and practitioners far beyond those included as authors, and we are grateful to all of you for your insights. This protocol was developed to provide a baseline for project-based monitoring of riverscape health and effectiveness of restoration actions related to low-tech process-based restoration (LTPBR) of riverscapes (<https://lowtechpbr.restoration.usu.edu>). It is a direct extension of a proof-of-concept by Weber et al. 2021 (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10631553](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10631553)).

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Summary

The following document provides a set of definitions and methods to describe the natural and anthropogenic characteristics of riverscapes. The intent is to offer riverscape researchers and restoration practitioners with a set protocol for planning and communicating the design and monitoring of Low – Tech Process – Based Restoration ([LTPBR](#)) projects. LTPBR practices are intended to invoke a more resilient riverscape, capable of maintaining a diverse set of self-sustaining fluvial and riparian processes that benefit aquatic, terrestrial, and anthropogenic systems. The use of self-sustaining processes as a restoration target presents a new set of challenges for defining and framing restoration objectives, monitoring outcomes, and adaptive management strategies that facilitate achievement of those objectives. This document describes a set of methods that has been designed to meet these challenges by elaborating new and effective ways to measure project outcomes and quantify their success at the appropriate spatiotemporal scales. Following the precedent and ethos set by LTPBR practices themselves, this protocol also aims to be an accessible and economic tool that facilitates the widespread planning, implementation, and adaptive management of river restoration efforts.

A FRESHLY BUILT BEAVER DAM ANALOG ON THE UPPER WILLIAMSON RIVER IN KLAMATH COUNTY OREGON. THE LTPBR DESIGN AND MONITORING V2 PRESENTS STANDARDIZED TERMINOLOGY AND METHODS THAT SUPPORT CONSISTENT DOCUMENTATION AND COMMUNICATION OF LTPBR RESTORATION PROJECT DESIGNS AND MONITORING OF PROJECT OUTCOMES.

Contents

- 1 Introduction..... 1
 - 1.1 Promoting and Measuring Riverscape Health 2
 - 1.2 LTPBR Implementation and Monitoring Version 2.0 3
 - 1.3 QRIS –QGIS Riverscape Studio 3
 - 1.4 Riverscape Projects and Their Components 4
 - 1.4.1 Riverscape Project Component Names and Descriptions 5
 - 1.4.2 Riverscape Features and GIS Geometry Types 6
 - 1.4.3 Field Vs. Desktop GIS Data Capture 7
- 2 Riverscape Project Inputs..... 9
 - 2.1 Riverscapes – Your Valley Bottom and Project Boundary 10
 - 2.2 AOIs – Areas of Interest 11
 - 2.3 Sample Frames – Analytical Riverscapes Framework 12
 - 2.4 Profiles – Your Riverscape Length..... 15
 - 2.4.1 The Centerline Tool..... 16
 - 2.5 Cross Sections – Riverscape Transects..... 16
 - 2.6 Contexts – Your Project, Your Spatial Data 17
 - 2.7 Surfaces – A Snapshot of Riverscape Conditions 18
- 3 Data Capture Events..... 22
 - 3.1 Basic Data Capture Event Properties 22
 - 3.2 Data Capture Methods..... 25
 - 3.3 Dam Crests 28
 - 3.4 BRAT Vegetation Suitability 30
 - 3.5 SEM – Stream Evolution Model State 31
 - 3.6 Active Channels..... 34
 - 3.7 Channel Junctions 36
 - 3.8 Geomorphic Units 38
 - 3.9 Active Valley Bottom Extents..... 40
 - 3.10 Inundation Extents 42
 - 3.11 Vegetation Extents 43
 - 3.12 Structural Elements..... 44

3.13	Risk Potential.....	46
3.14	Recovery Potential	47
3.15	Restoration Planning with Data Capture Events.....	48
4	LTPBR Designs.....	50
4.1	Basic Design Properties.....	50
4.2	Design Layers	54
4.3	Structures.....	54
4.4	Structure Complexes.....	56
4.5	Zones of Influence.....	57
4.6	Observations	59
4.7	LTPBR As-Built Surveys.....	61
5	Analyses.....	62
5.1	Creating and Managing Analyses.....	62
5.1.1	Analysis Attributes and Specifications.....	62
5.1.2	Manually Entering Metric Values	63
5.1.3	Manual and Automated Metric Values	64
5.1.4	Metric Value Uncertainty	64
6	Protocols in Practice.....	66
6.1	Birch Creek Beaver Translocation	66
6.1.1	Birch Creek – Protocol Opportunities and Constraints.....	67
6.1.2	Birch Creek – Project Elements, Actions, and Outcomes	67
6.2	Willow Springs Salmonid Habitat Restoration	69
6.2.1	Willow Springs – Protocol Opportunities and Constraints	70
6.2.2	Willow Springs – Project Elements, Actions, and Outcomes.....	70
7	References.....	73
8	Appendixes.....	75
8.1	Appendix I – LTPBR Structure Types	75
8.2	Appendix II – LTPBR Design Zones of Influence Types.....	79
8.3	Appendix III – Riverscape Metrics.....	80

Figures

Figure 1. A construction crew installing a post – assisted log structure (PALS) within a straightened and simplified channel. PALS are a common LTPBR structural treatment type that use many small pieces of large wood debris pinned together to mimic the form and function of larger woody debris pieces or woody debris aggregates.	1
Figure 2. A series of post – assisted log structures (PALS) captured just after install on a Klamath River tributary in Central Oregon.	2
Figure 3. Healthy riverscapes have (i) space to interact within their valley bottom; (ii) natural flow, sediment, and vegetation regimes; and (iii) structure that forces complexity and creates diverse residence times for water, sediment, and vegetation. When these principles of riverscape health are fulfilled, riverscape benefits result (Glassic et al. <i>In Prep.</i>).....	3
Figure 4. A spatial data editing session using the QGIS Riverscape Studio (QRiS) plugin. QRiS supports the organization and symbolization of your LTPBR design and monitoring data, allowing you can focus on describing your riverscapes and avoiding the tedium associated with management of GIS data.	4
Figure 5. Creation of a ‘New Project’ from the QGIS Riverscapes Studio (QRiS) toolbar. A project will house all of the designs, monitoring data, analyses, and supplemental spatial data that make up a riverscape project. Creation of a ‘project’ is the first step in your application of this riverscapes monitoring and implementation support framework.....	5
Figure 6. Examples of well thought out names and descriptions for QRiS riverscape project components. Names and descriptions are universal attributes that every QARiS project component uses. Users should strive to use names and descriptions that will help with future interpretation and utilization of your riverscape project Input (2) layers, Data Capture Events (3), LTPBR designs, and analyses.	6
Figure 7. Monitoring survey data and LTPBR designs are represented geospatially using point, line, and polygon vector geometries, and some riverscape feature types can be represented using multiple geometry types. For examples, natural and artificial beaver dams might be represented by points but could also be represented by lines that would provide a measure of the dam crest length and convey orientation.	7
Figure 8. Comparison of riverscapes with varying channel sizes and vegetative cover. The channel on the left is large and has little to no canopy cover allowing riverscape feature delineation to be effective on a desktop GIS. In contrast, the riverscape on the right has a small active channel and dense riparian vegetation. This riverscape setting would allow mapping of riparian vegetation using a desktop GIS, but would require a field survey to map in-channel geomorphic units, active channel extents, and other riverscape features.	8
Figure 9. Inputs lay the foundation for your QRiS projects and will be used throughout application of this protocol as the basis for monitoring, design, and the generation of analyses of your riverscape data.....	9
Figure 10. Example of a single feature ‘riverscape’ within QRiS. Riverscapes are a protocol concept that are used to represent the your project area extent. Riverscapes may consist of a single feature or multiple features that represent different reaches.2.7	10
Figure 11. The raster slider can be invoked within the QRiS plugin to export a valley bottom (i.e., riverscape) approximation from an existing surface raster. Approximate valley bottom might be exported from a	

detrended elevation model (REM) or could be exported from a VBET valley bottom probability surface.	11
Figure 12. Example of using an AOI to ‘clip’ a spatial dataset on import into a QRiS project. In this case the existing dam capacity from a BRAT model output is imported for just the project area.	12
Figure 13. Examples of Sample Frames within a QRiS project. Both examples show the lateral extent to be the approximate valley bottom. The left panel example shows Sample Frames that are specific to an experimental monitoring design containing treatment and control reaches. On the right, Sample Frames are segmented at 100 m intervals for an entire riverscape network allowing a longitudinal summary of riverscape attributes.	13
Figure 14. Menus showing the creation of a new set of Sample Frames by importing an existing feature class. .	14
Figure 15. Generating a new Sample Frame from existing QRiS layers. In this case a valley bottom polygon previously clipped to an AOI (2.2) is subdivided using Cross-Section (2.5) features that transect the riverscape.	14
Figure 16. Example of a manually digitized Profile representing the centerline and length of a project area.....	15
Figure 17. Invoking the centerline tool in QRiS to generate a centerline Profile for a valley bottom polygon. The tool requires as inputs a polygon feature (generally representing the valley bottom) and specification of a start and stop transect. The tool can provide a much more accurate and expedited centerline for complex valley bottoms or other polygons representing riverscape features.	16
Figure 18. Generation of Cross Sections at regular intervals along an existing channel profile (e.g., 100 m) can be used to create Sample Frames that allow summarizing the longitudinal distribution of riverscape data.	17
Figure 19. Contexts allow the import of any vector or raster spatial dataset into your riverscape project that isn’t an explicit part of the standard QRiS project layers (i.e., Inputs, The Data Capture Events (3), and LTPBR Designs). Any Contexts layer can also be ‘promoted’ for use as an AOI (2.2), Sample Frame (2.3), or Valley Bottom (2.1).....	18
Figure 20. Google Earth imagery, consumer drone orthomosaic, a hillshade raster, and a relative elevation model (REM) from LiDAR elevation data. All of these raster datasets are examples of geospatial data that can be utilized as a Surface in any Data Capture Event (3) or design specification (4). Sources may include any raster data type including aerial imagery, elevation data, or land cover distribution datasets.	19
Figure 21. Surfaces are raster datasets that provide the basis for implementation of Data Capture Methods (3.2) and development of LTPBR designs (4) using GIS software. Surfaces can consist of a variety of raster data types that include but are not limited to orthoimagery, elevation models (DEMs), or land-cover classification datasets.....	20
Figure 22. Example of a raster Surface layer, in this case a LiDAR DEM, that has been clipped to a project Area of Interest on import into a QRiS project. Using AOIs to reduce the extent of your imported raster Surfaces ensures can reduce the size of your QRiS projects saving disk space and improving the performance of GIS operations.	21
Figure 23. Specification of a new Data Capture Event (DCE) in QRiS. DCEs hold observations of riverscape conditions at discrete time periods and provide the foundation for describing the historic, current, and future potential for LTPBR projects.....	22
Figure 24. The QRiS interface for specification of basic attributes during creation of a new DCE.	23

Figure 25. Example of a well written DCE description that describes the Surfaces (2.7) and Data Capture Methods (3.2) that are being used by the DCE..... 24

Figure 26. QRiS interface for adding one or more available methods to a DCE. Your choice of which Data Capture Methods to employ on your project should be linked to your project objectives and recovery goals. 24

Figure 27. Example of dam crest mapping. Dam crests represent the lateral profile of natural or artificial beaver dams and are most easily mapped using high-resolution imagery within QRiS. 28

Figure 28. Examples of the Dam State attribute of Dam Crest features. dam state describes the dam with respect to its condition and ability to alter hydraulics..... 29

Figure 29. Aerial classification of vegetation suitability for beaver from predominately sagebrush (unsuitable) to willow and emergent aquatic vegetation (Preferred)..... 30

Figure 30. Conceptual diagram highlighting stream evolution model (SEM) stages as proposed by Cluer and Thorne (2014). As noted by the authors, it may take decades for or longer for a stream to transition between stages. In many cases, LTPBR is meant to expedite the time of riverscapes to progress to later SEM stages that feature greater aquatic habitat quantity, quality, and aquatic ecosystem services. 32

Figure 31. Classification of a riverscape into SEM stages as described by Cluer and Thorne (2014). Many LTPBR projects are meant to expedite the transition of degraded riverscapes into latter SEM stages that offer greater aquatic habitat and ecosystem benefits..... 33

Figure 32. Delineation of the active channel extent allows tracking and visualizing the dynamics of aquatic habitat expansion and increasing riverscape complexity. 34

Figure 33. Example of the difference in mapping the active channel as a centerline (Red) vs following the channel thalweg (Blue). 35

Figure 34. Example of mapping primary and non-primary (i.e., secondary) active channel lines. Mapping the active channel using lines allows quantification of channel length, and also allows calculation of metrics of channel complexity including sinuosity and the ratio of primary to non-primary channels. 36

Figure 35. Channel junction mapping offers an accessible approach to documenting the formation of anabranches within your riverscape. The method can be implemented either within GIS software or during field surveys. 37

Figure 36. Bed topography (shape) of in-channel geomorphic unit types adapted from Wheaton et al. 2015..... 38

Figure 37. A mosaic of geomorphic unit polygons within a highly complex section of channel. Geomorphic units can also be mapped as points in the field or on a desktop GIS to minimize survey time requirements... 39

Figure 38. Delineation of Active Extents being the combined area of the valley bottom that would be classified as active channel and active floodplain..... 41

Figure 39. Example of inundation mapping around a beaver dam. Inundation mapping can be used to produce metrics that are relevant to increasing aquatic habitat complexity, floodplain connectivity, and aquatic habitat capacity. 42

Figure 40. View of areas dominated by riparian and wetland vegetation digitized on aerial imagery. 43

Figure 41. QRiS interface for mapping the distribution of structural elements. Structural elements can be mapped as points, lines, or as polygons that signify an area containing multiple woody debris jams or a complex of beaver dams or artificial BDA structures..... 44

Figure 42. Approximation of structural element dimensions for a post assisted log structure (PALS). Structure dimensions can be used to develop a variety of metrics of structural element abundances such as total wood volume or summarizing the size and hydraulic influence of beaver dams within a complex or project area. 45

Figure 43. Risk and Recovery potential mapping is a key part of the LTPBR planning process and is used to communicate and quantify the space within the valley bottom that is available for expansion of aquatic habitat (Recovery Potential), or where sensitive infrastructure might be at risk to flooding or channel adjustment (Risk Potential). 46

Figure 44. The QRiS software allows specification of Data Capture Events into planning ‘Containers’ that are used to depict historic, contemporary, and potential future riverscape conditions that might result from a specific restoration design or management scenario. 48

Figure 45. A series of Data Capture Events used to communicate potential restoration outcomes as part of the restoration planning process. In this case, the Data Capture Events show the contemporary as well as two hypothetical future outcomes for the Active Valley Bottom Extent (3.9) and Active Channel (3.6) Extent within the Valley Bottom at between 1 – 4 years and 5 – 10 years following restoration implementation. Planning Data Capture Events can be used to develop reasonable expectations for indicators of project effectiveness. 49

Figure 46. Design creation within the QRiS toolbar interface. Designs are a sub-type of Data Capture Events with their own specific set of methods that support planning, designing, and surveying structures as they were constructed. 50

Figure 47. Basic properties common to all designs that provide context to the design’s creation and purpose... 51

Figure 48. Descriptive narratives describing the how and why of any design iteration provide context for future interpretation and collaboration on design resources..... 52

Figure 49. Design bases allow association of LTPBR designs with raster Surfaces (2.7) and Data Capture Events (3) that are a part of the same QRiS project. While evidence rasters are used to inform the design, associated Data Capture Events (3) are used to communicate the historic, contemporary, and potential future riverscape conditions that might be a design outcome. 53

Figure 50. QRiS interface for specification of layers that will be used to represent LTPBR project components. Designs can contain all or just one layer depending on the level of design needed. 54

Figure 51. LTPBR structure design specification as represented by line and point geometries. While slightly more arduous to map efficiently, lines geometry can be used to communicate approximate structure crest dimensions, positioning, or design intention for hydraulic or geomorphic influence. 55

Figure 52. Example of how groups of structures are placed into complex polygons that depict an approximate construction footprint within your riverscape. The complex concept provides a useful scale of project organization that can be used for developing coarse design plans, anticipating material staging, and directing construction crew effort. 56

Figure 53. Comparing two elements of LTPBR designs. Structure complexes (Left) show the approximate area of construction for a collection of structures that might share similar objectives, constraints, or logistics. While similar, zones of influence (ZOIs, Right) show expected hydraulic or geomorphic area that may be influenced as a result of the restoration design. ZOIs can be specified at either the complex level or for individual structures. Unlike complexes, ZOIs need not be mutually exclusive. 57

Figure 54. Several complex scale (i.e., groups of structures) ZOIs. Unlike Complexes, ZOI polygons will often overlap as different structure complexes are often designed to work together to enhance processes that support broader restoration goals by invoking a number of hydraulic or geomorphic processes..... 58

Figure 55. Example of point, line, and polygon observations showing logistical, cautionary, and opportunistic features around a project. Common uses of observations layers include marking access roads for travel, parking areas, sensitive human infrastructure, dangerous areas, and channel and floodplain riverscape features that might be considered within a structural treatment design. 59

Figure 56. Symbology for the observation type categories for point, line, and polygon data types..... 60

Figure 57. Creation of a new As-Built survey. As Built surveys are a sub-type of LTPBR designs that contain only structure layers and that capture the distribution and types of LTPBR structures that have been constructed..... 61

Figure 58. Specification of a new 'Analysis' of riverscape data. Analyses require at least one Sample Frame (2.3) and at least one Data Capture Event that contains a set of digitized observations, assessments, or an LTPBR design. 62

Figure 59. The QRiS analysis framework allows individual metrics to be specified as a 'Metric', 'Indicator', or 'None' so as not to be included in the analysis. 63

Figure 60. Values for indicator metrics can be manually entered, which is especially useful for Data Capture Events (3) that are intended to represent expected future or historic riverscape conditions. 64

Figure 61. The QRiS analysis framework allows storing manually entered and calculated values for each metric. The interface uses a combination of blue and orange circles and squares to indicate which values are being stored and also which values are currently being displayed and will be used to create reports, graphs, and value exports. 64

Figure 62. Overhead view of the riverscape within the Birch Creek project area on Google Earth imagery. Except for one clearing at a now established beaver complex the channel is difficult to see because of a forested valley bottom. The valley bottom layer uses the VBET approximation with a profile representing the valley bottom centerline drawn by hand. 67

Figure 63. Mapping the distribution of artificial and natural dams within the project area provides a clear indication that beaver translocation and BDA implementation were successful in meeting project goals of establishing persistent beaver colonies within then project area on Birch Creek. 68

Figure 64. Number of BDAs built as documented by As-Built (4.7) surveys, and number of natural beaver dams as documented by Data Capture Events (3) for the Birch Creek beaver translocation project. It is easy to see that although no new structural elements were implemented past 2017 the number of dams continues to grow as beaver colonies became established within the project area..... 69

Figure 65. The Willow Springs Preserve on Whychus Creek in central OR. The restoration project is focused on using structural treatments to increase in-channel habitat complexity, expanding riparian and wetland vegetation, and accelerate riverscape recovery toward a stage-0 condition. 69

Figure 66. The Willow Springs restoration project uses several Design, Monitoring, and Planning DCEs to organize riverscape information that was used during each phase of the project. 70

Figure 67. Examples of how riverscape features were mapped on repeat imagery acquisitions of the project area. Mapping riverscape features using GIS software is the primary approach for effectiveness monitoring on this project..... 71

Figure 68. Pre and Post structural treatment monitoring outcomes for the Willow Springs riverscape restoration project. The plots show that the restoration treatments resulted in an increase in bar, pool, and total channel geomorphic units and also woody debris jams within the project area. 72

Tables

Table 1. Data Capture Methods that make up the protocol’s observation and assessment monitoring approaches. One or more Data Capture Method will be employed within each of your project’s temporally discrete Data Capture Events.	26
Table 2. List of in-channel geomorphic units, their associated bedforms, and brief descriptions used in their delineation.....	39
Table 3. Layers, their description, and geometries used to represent LTPBR design components.....	54
Table 4. Overview of how different Birch Creek restoration and monitoring components are represented within this protocols implementation and monitoring framework.	67
Table 5. Overview of Willow Springs project elements and how they are represented within the LTPBR implementation and monitoring framework.	71

1 Introduction

Over recent decades LTPBR practices have gained broad appeal among riverscape restoration practitioners, and for good reason. The LTPBR approach operates in sharp contrast to more traditional stream restoration practices that rely on precise engineering plans (based on simplified fluvial models) and heavy construction equipment (i.e., excavators, skid-steer, etc.) to impose a desired form on streams and their accompanying floodplains. Put simply, LTPBR emphasizes restoration of available space and enhancement of processes inherent of unique riverscape settings. In this definition, 'space' refers to the amount of valley bottom available to the sometimes-wondering nature of stream channels and their floodplains. The practice seeks to enhance 'processes' through utilization of simple, cost-effective, often hand-built structures that mimic beaver dams (i.e., beaver dam analogs, or BDAs), wood accumulations (i.e., post-assisted log structures, or PALS), or other structural elements that naturally occur within aquatic systems. Structural elements are introduced to a river system in a design intended to amplify natural hydraulic, hydrologic, geomorphic, and vegetative processes that accelerate and ultimately sustain the recovery of degrade riverscapes. This approach reduces design and implementation costs, as well as the risks associated with the imposition of a semi-permanent form onto our inherently dynamic riverscapes. Lower design and implementation costs combined with reduced ecological and economic risks allows restoration practitioners to initiative a greater number of projects on a greater extent of river and stream networks with the hope of meeting the vast scale of aquatic habitat degradation.

FIGURE 1. A CONSTRUCTION CREW INSTALLING A POST – ASSISTED LOG STRUCTURE (PALS) WITHIN A STRAIGHTENED AND SIMPLIFIED CHANNEL. PALS ARE A COMMON LTPBR STRUCTURAL TREATMENT TYPE THAT USE MANY SMALL PIECES OF LARGE WOOD DEBRIS PINNED TOGETHER TO MIMIC THE FORM AND FUNCTION OF LARGER WOODY DEBRIS PIECES OR WOODY DEBRIS AGGREGATES.

Now that we know what LTPBR is, what is this protocol intended to do? In short, this protocol was designed to enable and standardize two project components that are essential to the practice and to the growing number of LTPBR restoration practitioners that include:

1. Supporting a consistent framework for creating and managing the information required to plan, implement, and adaptively manage Low-Tech Process-Based Riverscape restoration actions.
2. Providing an accessible and standardized set of methods for monitoring project outcomes and analyzing restoration effectiveness or riverscape health (see [1.1 Promoting and Measuring Riverscape Health](#)).

While the framework may be applicable to a variety of riverscape management and research contexts, the methods and concepts are most closely aligned with tenants of process – based restoration outlined by (Beechie et al. 2010), those of ecological restoration proposed by Palmer et al. (2005), and their extension as Low – Tech Process – Based Restoration (LTPBR) as outlined by Wheaton and others (2019). This protocol extends and operationalizes those ideas by proposing a set of data capture methods for documenting restoration project components and monitoring project outcomes in a consistent and standardized approach.

FIGURE 2. A SERIES OF POST – ASSISTED LOG STRUCTURES (PALS) CAPTURED JUST AFTER INSTALL ON A KLAMATH RIVER TRIBUTARY IN CENTRAL OREGON.

1.1 Promoting and Measuring Riverscape Health

The survey methods and associated survey metrics and indicators that have been included within this protocol were developed concurrently with contemporary efforts to refine and communicate a guiding set of riverscape health principles (Glassic et al., *In Prep.*). A close link between this protocol and a clearly articulated set of riverscape health principles should facilitate what is monitored to objectively assess the status and trends of riverscape conditions in relation to policy objectives. The principles can be applied to help identify which aspect of health are missing in a particular riverscape setting and allow realistic goals and objectives to be established

for management, conservation, and restoration actions. This link will also facilitate discussions with landowners and managers about the appropriateness of management actions and potential outcomes of management changes or restoration actions. Riverscape health principles and their relationship to indicators obtained via this protocol will also allow prioritization and design of riverscape restoration and management actions across a variety of spatial scales, allowing for defensible, efficient resource allocation to address limiting factors and restore ecosystem benefits, advancing the needs of multiple interested and affected parties.

FIGURE 3. HEALTHY RIVERSCAPES HAVE (I) SPACE TO INTERACT WITHIN THEIR VALLEY BOTTOM; (II) NATURAL FLOW, SEDIMENT, AND VEGETATION REGIMES; AND (III) STRUCTURE THAT FORCES COMPLEXITY AND CREATES DIVERSE RESIDENCE TIMES FOR WATER, SEDIMENT, AND VEGETATION. WHEN THESE PRINCIPLES OF RIVERSCAPE HEALTH ARE FULFILLED, RIVERSCAPE BENEFITS RESULT (GLASSIC ET AL. *IN PREP.*).

1.2 LTPBR Implementation and Monitoring Version 2.0

The first iteration of this protocol, [LTPBR IMP v1](#), was completed in 2022. While v1 was designed with a similar intent as v2, there exists several fundamental differences in their scope and application. Most notably, the v1 protocol had greater emphasis on classifying the characteristics and behavior of individual project features (e.g., LTPBR structures, natural dams). Also, as a proof of concept, v1.0 was built as a FileMaker Pro Database application, and while it was able to spatially reference riverscape observations attributes, was not an explicitly geospatial approach to riverscape assessment. In contrast, the v2 protocol places more focus on the type and spatiotemporal distribution of riverscape features that are created by fluvial processes and therefore, indicative of riverscape health.

Mapping and classification of riverscape restoration actions and features are central to the efficiency and effectiveness of the V2 protocol. Riverscape features are created and maintained by riverscape processes, and the type, distribution, and abundance of riverscape features provides direct insight to the extent that key processes are active.

1.3 QRiS –QGIS Riverscape Studio

The [QGIS Riverscape Studio](#), or QRiS (pronounced ‘curious’) is a plugin for the open-sourced desktop GIS software QGIS. QRiS has been designed from the ground up to support application of this and similar protocols that leverage spatial data and GIS standards to describe the collection of features and landforms that make up a riverscape. QGIS and the QRiS plugin are totally free and cross-platform, so virtually

anyone can with a computer and internet access can pick up this protocol and get started designing and monitoring LTPBR projects using a consistent framework for capturing, organizing, visualizing, and analyzing riverscape information. QRiS is meant to handle much of the tedium associated with managing and analyzing GIS data, allowing practitioners to focus on developing LTPBR project designs and monitoring LTPBR project outcomes.

FIGURE 4. A SPATIAL DATA EDITING SESSION USING THE QGIS RIVERSCAPE STUDIO (QRiS) PLUGIN. QRiS SUPPORTS THE ORGANIZATION AND SYMBOLIZATION OF YOUR LTPBR DESIGN AND MONITORING DATA, ALLOWING YOU CAN FOCUS ON DESCRIBING YOUR RIVERSCAPES AND AVOIDING THE TEDIUM ASSOCIATED WITH MANAGEMENT OF GIS DATA.

1.4 Riverscape Projects and Their Components

Within this framework and its representation in the QRiS supporting software, the concept of a [‘project’](#) functions as the highest-level of organization. Every piece of monitoring data you collect, each piece of geospatial data you import, and every analysis you specify will be associated with a project. Think of a ‘project’ as your riverscape or your collection of riverscapes. In some cases, your project may focus on a single short stream reach (e.g., 500 m or 1 mile) while others may consider the channel network within an entire watershed. The creation of a ‘project’ within the QRiS GIS software represents your first step toward curation of geospatial datasets, development of LTPBR designs, collection of monitoring information, and the specification of analyses that describe the health of your riverscape or project area.

FIGURE 5. CREATION OF A 'NEW PROJECT' FROM THE QGIS RIVERSCAPES STUDIO (QRiS) TOOLBAR. A PROJECT WILL HOUSE ALL OF THE DESIGNS, MONITORING DATA, ANALYSES, AND SUPPLEMENTAL SPATIAL DATA THAT MAKE UP A RIVERSCAPE PROJECT. CREATION OF A 'PROJECT' IS THE FIRST STEP IN YOUR APPLICATION OF THIS RIVERSCAPES MONITORING AND IMPLEMENTATION SUPPORT FRAMEWORK.

The protocol and the treatment of riverscapes projects follow the following organizational structure that consists of:

- Section 2 covers [Riverscape Project Inputs](#), where you will start to build out your project by leveraging an assortment of user created and remotely sensed geospatial data that provides context for describing your riverscape and its change through time.
- Section 3 - [Data Capture Events](#) gives an explanation of each riverscape monitoring method and their use in documenting the abundance, distribution, and characteristics of features within your riverscape. Explanations include practical guidance and best practices for survey application based on feature types and riverscape setting (e.g., heavily forested vs. open canopy).
- Section 4 – [LTPBR Designs](#) covers the concepts and constructs used to document, communicate, and iterate on LTPBR structural treatment designs.
- Section 5 - [Analyses](#) brings together project Inputs, Data Capture Events, and Designs in the calculation of standard descriptive project metrics and indicators of project effectiveness.

1.4.1 Riverscape Project Component Names and Descriptions

It should now be apparent that this protocol and the QRiS supporting software allow for the curation and creation of geospatial data that include LTPBR designs, riverscape monitoring information, and analyses. The QRiS software is designed to handle much of the tedium associated with managing your project data over time. One of the strengths of this software is the ability to record contextual information about your project data that can help with the analysis and interpretation of project information years or even decades after its initial collection. Part of this contextual information is the ability for the user to provide descriptive names and descriptive narratives about each project component ([Figure 6](#)). These two attributes (i.e., name and description) are used by every piece of information within your riverscape project from project Inputs ([2](#)) to project Analyses ([5](#)). Whenever possible protocol users are encouraged to develop names and descriptions that highlight the how, why, and who behind every project component. Providing this type of information will ensure that your future self as well as your colleagues in riverscape management can take full advantage of the information that you create and curate within the QRiS software.

FIGURE 6. EXAMPLES OF WELL THOUGHT OUT NAMES AND DESCRIPTIONS FOR QRIS RIVERSCAPE PROJECT COMPONENTS. NAMES AND DESCRIPTIONS ARE UNIVERSAL ATTRIBUTES THAT EVERY QRIS PROJECT COMPONENT USES. USERS SHOULD STRIVE TO USE NAMES AND DESCRIPTIONS THAT WILL HELP WITH FUTURE INTERPRETATION AND UTILIZATION OF YOUR RIVERSCAPE PROJECT INPUT (2) LAYERS, DATA CAPTURE EVENTS (3), LTPBR DESIGNS, AND ANALYSES.

1.4.2 Riverscape Features and GIS Geometry Types

The design and survey protocols within this framework represent the geospatial distribution and form of riverscape features using standard GIS vector data types of points, lines, and polygons. GIS (i.e., geographic information systems) software represent features using three primary geometry types: points, lines, and polygons.

- **POINTS** capture the location of features without detailing their shape or orientation. Points are the most expedient geometry type to capture and are also the most ideal for mapping feature distribution during field surveys.
- **LINES** are really a series of linearly connected points representative of feature location, shape, length, and orientation. Line geometries are commonly used in the linear representation of the active channel centerline or thalweg, or the center of your riverscape (valley bottom) network.
- **POLYGONS** represent the location, shape, and spatial extent of riverscape features. Polygon geometries are ideal for mapping riverscape surfaces like the area of active floodplain, riparian vegetation extents, or even in-channel geomorphic units.

FIGURE 7. MONITORING SURVEY DATA AND LTPBR DESIGNS ARE REPRESENTED GEOSPATIALLY USING POINT, LINE, AND POLYGON VECTOR GEOMETRIES, AND SOME RIVERSCAPE FEATURE TYPES CAN BE REPRESENTED USING MULTIPLE GEOMETRY TYPES. FOR EXAMPLES, NATURAL AND ARTIFICIAL BEAVER DAMS MIGHT BE REPRESENTED BY POINTS BUT COULD ALSO BE REPRESENTED BY LINES THAT WOULD PROVIDE A MEASURE OF THE DAM CREST LENGTH AND CONVEY ORIENTATION.

More than one geometry type may be used to map the same riverscape feature type. For example, a natural or artificial beaver dam might be represented as a point to simply capture its location but could also be represented as a line which provides a representation of its crest length and orientation. Complete description of how this protocol represents riverscape features within monitoring surveys (3) and LTPBR designs (4) are found in [Table 1](#) and [Table 3](#).

1.4.3 Field Vs. Desktop GIS Data Capture

As discussed above, this protocol has been developed with a focus on documenting the spatial distribution and geometry of riverscape features, both with respect to developing restoration designs and monitoring their outcomes. The protocol methods can be implemented using a combination of desktop GIS software (usually QRIS) and using mobile GIS applications in the field (e.g., [ESRI AGOL field apps](#), [QField](#)). Each approach (i.e., desktop vs field data capture) has its own set of advantages and limitations depending on the riverscape setting and survey method (e.g., structural element mapping, active channel mapping). For example, even with high resolution imagery, a desktop GIS delineation of channel features or structural elements will not be possible in small streams with heavily forested canopies. Conversely, it would be difficult to map the aerial extent of riparian vegetation for long distances (i.e., miles) during field visits unless suitable vantage points are available for the entire project area. Understanding these limitations is critical for the application of this framework, and the appropriateness of each data collection method will be specific to the individual riverscape setting.

FIGURE 8. COMPARISON OF RIVERSCAPES WITH VARYING CHANNEL SIZES AND VEGETATIVE COVER. THE CHANNEL ON THE LEFT IS LARGE AND HAS LITTLE TO NO CANOPY COVER ALLOWING RIVERSCAPE FEATURE DELINEATION TO BE EFFECTIVE ON A DESKTOP GIS. IN CONTRAST, THE RIVERSCAPE ON THE RIGHT HAS A SMALL ACTIVE CHANNEL AND DENSE RIPARIAN VEGETATION. THIS RIVERSCAPE SETTING WOULD ALLOW MAPPING OF RIPARIAN VEGETATION USING A DESKTOP GIS, BUT WOULD REQUIRE A FIELD SURVEY TO MAP IN-CHANNEL GEOMORPHIC UNITS, ACTIVE CHANNEL EXTENTS, AND OTHER RIVERSCAPE FEATURES.

2 Riverscape Project Inputs

The aim of this protocol is to assist practitioners with the capture, management, and analysis of riverscape monitoring and LTPBR design information. These topics and their associated data capture methods are given a thorough treatment in the sections covering Data Capture Events (3) and LTPBR Designs (4). Another strength of this protocol lies in its ability to incorporate additional sources of geospatial data and tools into your riverscape monitoring and LTPBR design workflows development workflows. The QRIS software organizes these additional geospatial resources into selection of project Inputs, each intended to play specific roles in your riverscape project development, survey implementation, or analytics (Figure 9). While Inputs are not a requirement to start collecting survey data or creating LTPBR designs in QRIS, they do provide the foundation for effective riverscape survey data capture and generation of project summaries and analyses.

Don't get bogged down by all the concepts in this section. If you are just picking up this protocol and the QRIS software to mock up an LTPBR design or do a quick survey of orthoimagery you can skip to section 3 or section 4. You can revisit these concepts later when it's time to conduct more involved spatial analyses of your riverscape data.

FIGURE 9. INPUTS LAY THE FOUNDATION FOR YOUR QRIS PROJECTS AND WILL BE USED THROUGHOUT APPLICATION OF THIS PROTOCOL AS THE BASIS FOR MONITORING, DESIGN, AND THE GENERATION OF ANALYSES OF YOUR RIVERSCAPE DATA.

A general description for each Input type is provided below, and each description contains the following pieces of information:

INPUT GEOMETRIES – A description of how vector data types, including point, line, and/or polygons, are used to represent the Input features within your riverscape. Some Input types, such as those that consist strictly of raster datasets (e.g., orthoimagery, elevation models), will not have a vector geometry type.

INPUT ATTRIBUTES – All Input types possess **NAME** and **DESCRIPTION** attributes, and users should strive to use values that provide context for the layers use and significant within your QRiS project. Some Input types will have additional attributes that are used for specific purposes within your QRiS project.

INPUT SOURCES – Common means of acquiring or producing the Input data. For vector Input types, this might include hand mapping the feature within GIS software, importing features from an existing riverscapes model, or using the output of a geoprocessing tool within QRiS. For raster Input types, the source may refer to locations for acquiring elevation data, online repositories where landcover model outputs are available, or other raster data types that might fit each Input’s use.

INPUT APPLICATION – A short description of how the project input is intended to be used within the protocol. For example, how input features are used to represent LTPBR design reaches, to summarize spatial data in [Analyses](#), or to generate elevation profiles.

2.1 Riverscapes – Your Valley Bottom and Project Boundary

The Riverscapes Input type is used to represent the valley bottom or extent of your project. The term ‘riverscape’ is often loosely used to describe the area and features found along a river, where features include all natural (e.g., the channel, beaver dams, terraces) and anthropogenic landforms (e.g., houses, fields, fences). Geomorphologists generally use the term more explicitly to include the area and features that could potentially flood given the contemporary (i.e., current geologic and climatic conditions) flow regime, a definition that is often interchangeable with the term ‘valley bottom’.

FIGURE 10. EXAMPLE OF A SINGLE FEATURE ‘RIVERSCAPE’ WITHIN QRiS. RIVERSCAPES ARE A PROTOCOL CONCEPT THAT ARE USED TO REPRESENT THE YOUR PROJECT AREA EXTENT. RIVERSCAPES MAY CONSIST OF A SINGLE FEATURE OR MULTIPLE FEATURES THAT REPRESENT DIFFERENT REACHES. 2.7

Riverscapes Geometries

POLYGONS – Riverscapes are represented as polygons that will generally depict the lateral (i.e., current valley bottom) and longitudinal extent of your project ([Figure 10](#)).

Riverscapes Sources

Riverscapes can be manually mapped using GIS software and other spatial datasets such as orthoimagery, DEMs, or other raster datasets that provide evidence of the valley bottom. Importing valley bottom polygons generated by the [VBET model](#) can serve as a starting point for establishing riverscapes polygons within your project. The raster slider tool can be used with a relative elevation model (REM) to export an approximation of the valley bottom or other elevational surface based as the distance above the channel ([Figure 11](#)).

FIGURE 11. THE RASTER SLIDER CAN BE INVOKED WITHIN THE QRIS PLUGIN TO EXPORT A VALLEY BOTTOM (I.E., RIVERSCAPE) APPROXIMATION FROM AN EXISTING SURFACE RASTER. APPROXIMATE VALLEY BOTTOM MIGHT BE EXPORTED FROM A DETRENDED ELEVATION MODEL (REM) OR COULD BE EXPORTED FROM A [VBET VALLEY BOTTOM PROBABILITY SURFACE](#).

Riverscapes Application

As their name entails, Riverscapes are used to represent the extent of the valley bottom, and within a QRIS project they will represent your projects longitudinal and lateral extent. Riverscapes features are often used as a starting point for defining [Sample Frames](#) which form the basis for [Analyses](#) and the calculation of riverscape metrics and indicators.

2.2 AOIs – Areas of Interest

[Areas of Interest](#) (AOIs) are polygon features that can be used to limit the extent, or 'clip', any spatial dataset that is imported into your QRIS project. For example, you may want to import a national vegetation coverage raster dataset into your QRIS project, but only need it for the specific reach that you're working in. In this case you could take an AOI polygon that approximated the valley bottom of your project area and use it to clip the vegetation coverage layer to just that AOI area. You can have as many AOIs as needed in your project, which may include watershed boundaries, counties, or any other project areas for which you may want to limit your spatial data extent.

Figure 10

FIGURE 12. EXAMPLE OF USING AN AOI TO ‘CLIP’ A SPATIAL DATASET ON IMPORT INTO A QRIS PROJECT. IN THIS CASE THE EXISTING DAM CAPACITY FROM A BRAT MODEL OUTPUT IS IMPORTED FOR JUST THE PROJECT AREA.

AOI Geometries

AOIs are always represented by polygons. Each AOI layer can contain 1 or more polygon features.

AOI Sources

AOIs are typically boundaries such as watersheds, states, counties, or another geographic region. Your Riverscape (2.1) polygons can serve as an ideal AOI and can be used to reduce the extent of any spatial layer to your project valley bottom area. AOIs can also be mapped by hand.

AOI Application

AOIs are used to clip the extent of any input or data capture event layer as it is imported into your QRIS project. AOIs are capable of clipping either vector or raster spatial data types and might be invoked when importing spatial data into any Input or Data Capture Event layer.

2.3 Sample Frames – Analytical Riverscapes Framework

[Sample Frames](#) are polygon features that are used to divide your Riverscape (2.1) into smaller units that define the spatial extent of analyses and the calculation of metrics and indicators (see [5 Analyses](#)). Projects can have as many Sample Frames as are necessary and might divide your project area by geomorphic reach breaks, land ownership type, property owners, monitoring or restoration design reaches, or any other spatial segregation that is meaningful within your project ([Figure 13](#)).

FIGURE 13. EXAMPLES OF SAMPLE FRAMES WITHIN A QRIS PROJECT. BOTH EXAMPLES SHOW THE LATERAL EXTENT TO BE THE APPROXIMATE VALLEY BOTTOM. THE LEFT PANEL EXAMPLE SHOWS SAMPLE FRAMES THAT ARE SPECIFIC TO AN EXPERIMENTAL MONITORING DESIGN CONTAINING TREATMENT AND CONTROL REACHES. ON THE RIGHT, SAMPLE FRAMES ARE SEGMENTED AT 100 M INTERVALS FOR AN ENTIRE RIVERSCAPE NETWORK ALLOWING A LONGITUDINAL SUMMARY OF RIVERSCAPE ATTRIBUTES.

Sample Frame Geometries

Sample Frames are strictly limited to polygon geometries. For your Analyses to be meaningful the features in a single Sample Frame layer should be mutually exclusive (i.e. no overlap of polygons).

Sample Frame Attributes

Sample Frames include several attributes that define individual feature labels, topology, and longitudinal position within your riverscape. These attributes are also used when creating new Sample Frames from polygon layers that are already part of your QRIS project.

LABELS – Used to label individual Sample Frame features when added to the map.

FLOW PATH – Similar to a stream name or the level path attribute in NHDI. Generally used to define how polygons group with one another as tributaries or nodes in a stream network.

FIGURE 14. MENUS SHOWING THE CREATION OF A NEW SET OF SAMPLE FRAMES BY IMPORTING AN EXISTING FEATURE CLASS.

Sample Frame Sources

Sample Frame features can be created by manually digitizing your own features or importing features from an existing polygon feature class that is outside your QRIS project. Polygon features that are a part of your Riverscapes (2.1), AOIs (2.2), or Contexts (2.6) layers can all be used to as feature source for creation of new Sample Frames. Cross Section (2.5) layers can be used to subdivide polygon features when creating new Sample Frames (Figure 15).

FIGURE 15. GENERATING A NEW SAMPLE FRAME FROM EXISTING QRIS LAYERS. IN THIS CASE A VALLEY BOTTOM POLYGON PREVIOUSLY CLIPPED TO AN AOI (2.2) IS SUBDIVIDED USING CROSS-SECTION (2.5) FEATURES THAT TRANSECT THE RIVERSCAPE.

Sample Frame Application

Sample Frames subdivide your riverscape into meaningful units and in doing so they define the scope for Analyses (5) implemented within QRiS. Use a Sample Frame (2.3) with a single polygon feature that encompasses your entire project area to summarize LTPBR Design and Data Capture Event data project wide. Add another Sample Frame layer that divides your project by landowners, valley segments, or land management types to conduct more targeted analyses. QRiS projects can use as many Sample Frame layers as are needed to support generation of meaningful summaries and analyses of riverscape data.

2.4 Profiles – Your Riverscape Length

[Profiles](#) are line geometries that run parallel or longitudinally to your riverscape network and are commonly used to represent the center of your valley bottom (riverscape) and the valley length of your riverscape project.

Profile Geometries

Profile are strictly line geometry types that should run parallels to your riverscape network. In most cases they will be used to represent the center of your Riverscape (2.1) polygons.

Profile Application

Profiles are included in Analyses (5) to calculate metrics that are scaled to the riverscape network or length of your Sample Frames (2.3) within your project area (e.g., pools per km or dams per km). Profiles are also commonly used to generate Cross-Sections (2.5) that run perpendicular to the valley and are in turn used to support creation of Sample Frames.

FIGURE 16. EXAMPLE OF A MANUALLY DIGITIZED PROFILE REPRESENTING THE CENTERLINE AND LENGTH OF A PROJECT AREA.

Profile Sources

Profiles can be imported from existing feature classes but are more commonly mapped by hand (Figure 16) on orthoimagery or other Surface data types (2.7). Profile lines can also be generated from within QRIS using the Centerline Tool (2.4.1).

2.4.1 The Centerline Tool

The [Centerline Tool](#) automates generation of a line feature that runs down the center of a polygon and is therefore ideal for generating a centerline Profile of your Riverscapes (2.1) polygon features. The tool can be run on any QRIS Contexts or Riverscape (2.1) layer. The Centerline Tool can only be run on a single feature (as opposed to an entire layer with multiple polygon features) and simply requires user specification of an approximate (stop) upstream and downstream (start) transect (Figure 17).

FIGURE 17. INVOKING THE CENTERLINE TOOL IN QRIS TO GENERATE A CENTERLINE PROFILE FOR A VALLEY BOTTOM POLYGON. THE TOOL REQUIRES AS INPUTS A POLYGON FEATURE (GENERALLY REPRESENTING THE VALLEY BOTTOM) AND SPECIFICATION OF A START AND STOP TRANSECT. THE TOOL CAN PROVIDE A MUCH MORE ACCURATE AND EXPEDITED CENTERLINE FOR COMPLEX VALLEY BOTTOMS OR OTHER POLYGONS REPRESENTING RIVERSCAPE FEATURES.

2.5 Cross Sections – Riverscape Transects

[Cross Sections](#) transect your riverscape. They are line geometries that run perpendicular to the valley or channel (Figure 18) and can be used to subdivide other project layers (i.e., Sample Frames 2.3) and to generate elevation profiles.

Cross Sections Geometries

Cross Section features are strictly represented by line type geometries. In most cases Cross Section features should be running perpendicular to your valley bottom or to the channel. Cross Sections features should extend beyond the features that they are meant to transect.

Cross Sections Application

The primary use of Cross Section features is to subdivide polygons during the creation of new Sample Frame layers (2.3). This is done by specifying a Cross Section layer from your QRiS project during the creation of a new Sample Frame. Be sure that your Cross Section lines extend outside the polygon features that are being subdivided. Cross Sections can also be used to generate channel elevation profiles using a digital elevation model.

Cross Sections Sources

Cross Section lines can be manually mapped within your QRiS project. When Cross Section lines are used to generate Sample Frames (2.3), they should be placed at point that define breaks riverscape characters, ownership, study designs, or any other criteria for subdividing your riverscape. They should also extend outside the extent of the polygon features that will be subdivided.

Cross Section lines can also be generated at regular intervals along a channel Profile (2.4) in your QRiS project. Generation of Cross Sections requires specification of an interval and width. For example, the tool could be asked to create Cross Sections at 100 m intervals along a Profile with each Cross Section feature being that are all 100 m in wide (Figure 18). Generating cross-sections at regular intervals allows generation of Sample Frames (2.3) that can be used to produce longitudinal summaries of your Data Capture Event observations (3) or LTPBR Designs (4).

FIGURE 18. GENERATION OF CROSS SECTIONS AT REGULAR INTERVALS ALONG AN EXISTING CHANNEL PROFILE (E.G., 100 M) CAN BE USED TO CREATE SAMPLE FRAMES THAT ALLOW SUMMARIZING THE LONGITUDINAL DISTRIBUTION OF RIVERSCAPE DATA.

2.6 Contexts – Your Project, Your Spatial Data

Until this point, project Inputs have each had an explicit role in this protocol or the QRiS software, with each Input type either representing specific riverscape features or supporting analyses. While these specific use cases

are comprehensive, the QRIS software has been designed to allow utilization of unanticipated geospatial datasets that do not fit neatly into one of the standard Input constructs, but that might be essential for the description and contextualization of your riverscape project. Examples of useful geospatial riverscape datasets are many but might include vegetation land-cover raster or vector dataset, a species of concern historic or current distribution, or past field data collection efforts. These generic vector and raster datasets can be housed within the [Contexts](#) portion of the QRIS software panel ([Figure 19](#)), and there is no limit to the number of Context layers that can be imported into your project. Context layers can also be promoted to other Input layer types such as Riverscapes, AOIs, or Sample Frames.

FIGURE 19. CONTEXTS ALLOW THE IMPORT OF ANY VECTOR OR RASTER SPATIAL DATASET INTO YOUR RIVERSCAPE PROJECT THAT ISN'T AN EXPLICIT PART OF THE STANDARD QRIS PROJECT LAYERS (I.E., INPUTS, THE DATA CAPTURE EVENTS (3), AND LTPBR DESIGNS). ANY CONTEXTS LAYER CAN ALSO BE 'PROMOTED' FOR USE AS AN AOI (2.2), SAMPLE FRAME (2.3), OR VALLEY BOTTOM (2.1).

2.7 Surfaces – A Snapshot of Riverscape Conditions

[Surfaces](#) are raster datasets that provide a snapshot of riverscape conditions specific to a period of time. They are used in QRIS to support GIS delineation of riverscape features and development of LTPBR Designs.

FIGURE 20. GOOGLE EARTH IMAGERY, CONSUMER DRONE ORTHOMOSAIC, A HILLSHADE RASTER, AND A RELATIVE ELEVATION MODEL (REM) FROM LIDAR ELEVATION DATA. ALL OF THESE RASTER DATASETS ARE EXAMPLES OF GEOSPATIAL DATA THAT CAN BE UTILIZED AS A SURFACE IN ANY DATA CAPTURE EVENT (3) OR DESIGN SPECIFICATION (4). SOURCES MAY INCLUDE ANY RASTER DATA TYPE INCLUDING AERIAL IMAGERY, ELEVATION DATA, OR LAND COVER DISTRIBUTION DATASETS.

There are innumerable sources and types of raster datasets available to the riverscape restoration and monitoring practitioner, and their application within your QRiS riverscape projects is limited only by your creativity and analytical imagination. Common raster datasets will include but are not limited to satellite imagery, drone acquired orthomosaics, digital elevation models, land-cover datasets, or other types of raster data (Figure 20). Repeat acquisitions of Surfaces can be an important monitoring tool to track changes to your riverscapes over time. Some Data Capture Methods (3.2) that are an integral component of this protocol are exclusively conducted within a GIS platform, and the Surfaces within your project provide the primary source of context to digitize, survey, and assess features and conditions within your riverscape.

If you are using orthoimagery to track changes to your riverscape it is important to georeference the imagery acquisitions collected over time to one another. This allows riverscape features digitized from one imagery acquisition date to be directly comparable to others.

Surface Attributes

Surfaces contain several attributes that describe their data type, acquisition method, their source, and context and relevance for inclusion in your Data Capture Events (3) and LTPBR Designs (4).

FIGURE 21. SURFACES ARE RASTER DATASETS THAT PROVIDE THE BASIS FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF DATA CAPTURE METHODS (3.2) AND DEVELOPMENT OF LTPBR DESIGNS (4) USING GIS SOFTWARE. SURFACES CAN CONSIST OF A VARIETY OF RASTER DATA TYPES THAT INCLUDE BUT ARE NOT LIMITED TO ORTHOIMAGERY, ELEVATION MODELS (DEMs), OR LAND-COVER CLASSIFICATION DATASETS.

RASTER TYPE – Selection of common raster dataset types that are often used to inform riverscape designs and monitoring assessments. In some cases specification of the raster type allows QRiS to display the raster with specific symbology.

DETRENDED SURFACE – A detrended elevation model (e.g., relative elevation model, Height Above Nearest Drainage).

DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL – DEM surfaces such as nationally available 10 m elevations, LiDAR elevation data, or an elevation surface generated through topographic surveys or photogrammetry.

GEOMORPHIC CHANGE DETECTION – A DEM of difference (DoD), commonly generated using [GCD software](#).

HILLSHADE – Shaded relief of terrain used in the visualization of elevation surfaces. Hillshade raster surfaces are created by default when importing any DEM as a Surface in QRiS.

SATELLITE – Any satellite acquired orthoimagery.

SLOPE RASTER – A raster surface where each cell depicts inclination from horizontal, can be expressed as degrees or as a percent.

VALLEY BOTTOM EVIDENCE – A raster surfaced produced by the [VBET tool](#) in which each cell represents a probability of being a part of the valley bottom.

FIGURE 22. EXAMPLE OF A RASTER SURFACE LAYER, IN THIS CASE A LiDAR DEM, THAT HAS BEEN CLIPPED TO A PROJECT AREA OF INTEREST ON IMPORT INTO A QRIS PROJECT. USING AOIS TO REDUCE THE EXTENT OF YOUR IMPORTED RASTER SURFACES ENSURES CAN REDUCE THE SIZE OF YOUR QRIS PROJECTS SAVING DISK SPACE AND IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF GIS OPERATIONS.

RASTER SOURCE – An attribute that provides a more targeted description of the Surface’s origin or means or data acquisition. Values generally consist of a selection of raster data types that will commonly be incorporated into in your riverscape projects.

RIVERSCAPE PROJECT – An output from one of the standard riverscape models (e.g., [VBET](#), [TAUDEM](#)) curated by the [Riverscapes Consortium](#).

SATELLITE – Remotely sensed information used to generate the raster surface was acquired by a satellite.

DRONE – Remotely sensed information used to generate the raster surface was acquired by a drone.

DRONEDEPLOY – Raster surface is a product (e.g., orthoimagery, plant health, elevation) generated by the DroneDeploy UAV mapping platform.

PLEADIES-NEO SATELLITE – Raster surface was acquired by the Pleadies-Neo Satellite constellation which collects daily planet-wide multi-spectral imagery.

DERIVED – Raster surface was derived within the QRiS software (e.g., slope analysis or imagery classification).

OTHER – The raster is not one of the standard sources. The raster source should be described in the description for the Surface layer.

CLIP TO AOI – Specifies an AOI ([2.2](#)) that will be used for clipping the raster extent on import ([Figure 22](#)).

ACQUISITION DATE – Date of remotely sensed data or imagery acquisition such as the date of a drone flight or date that LiDAR elevation data was acquired. Surfaces often provide the basis for Data Capture Events ([3](#)), and the Acquisition Date in many cases should correspond with the time period associated with a DCE.

3 Data Capture Events

Monitoring under this protocol is based on the premise that the presence, distribution, and characteristics of riverscape features can provide direct and indirect evidence of the presence of healthy riverscape processes (Glassic et al. *In Prep.*). The protocol and its supporting QRiS software have been designed to allow efficient and streamlined capture and management of riverscape feature observations and riverscape assessment with the intent of supporting practitioners in assessing riverscape health and restoration effectiveness over time.

FIGURE 23. SPECIFICATION OF A NEW DATA CAPTURE EVENT (DCE) IN QRiS. DCEs HOLD OBSERVATIONS OF RIVERSCAPE CONDITIONS AT DISCRETE TIME PERIODS AND PROVIDE THE FOUNDATION FOR DESCRIBING THE HISTORIC, CURRENT, AND FUTURE POTENTIAL FOR LTPBR PROJECTS.

QRiS supports the management of riverscape surveys and assessments by organizing them into temporally discrete Data Capture Events. A Data Capture Event might consist of an afternoon spent surveying structural element distributions (i.e., natural and artificial beaver dams and woody debris jams), or mapping primary and anabranch channels and riparian vegetation extents from drone imagery in the years following a restoration treatment. Any riverscape project can have as many Data Capture Events staged through time as are needed, and each Data Capture Event can consist of one or more monitoring Data Capture Methods (Table 1). The QRiS software also supports development of hypothetical Planning Data Capture Events that are used to establish and communicate approximations of historic or expected future riverscape conditions and indicator values that might be realized following riverscape recovery.

3.1 Basic Data Capture Event Properties

All Data Capture Events (DCEs) begin with the specification of some basic attributes including a descriptive name, temporal context, and the designation of associated Data Capture Methods (3.2) and raster Surfaces (2.7).

FIGURE 24. THE QRIS INTERFACE FOR SPECIFICATION OF BASIC ATTRIBUTES DURING CREATION OF A NEW DCE.

DCE NAME – A descriptive name for the DCE. Strive to use a name that adds context to the DCE. For example, a name such as ‘2024 Drone Imagery Acquisition’ provides enough detail to inform that the DCE is going to be based on observations and assessments from imagery captured during the summer of 2024.

QRIS will allow you rename or change any of your project attributes at any time so you can focus on describing your riverscape and spend less time on data management and worrying about specifying the perfect DCE Name on creation!

DCE DATE – DCEs are an account of riverscape conditions over discrete time periods. When appropriate, such as when the DCE is associated with a single imagery acquisition or day of field data collection, dates may be specified with a high degree of precision, but they can also be specified more generally. For example, a year (e.g., 1900s) may be used to represent historic riverscape conditions, or a year and a month (e.g., 2025 - July) to refer to a field data collection campaign that occurred over a longer period or season.

DESCRIPTION – Descriptive narrative that helps contextualize a DCE within an LTPBR project (Figure 25). Descriptions can and should contain information on how historic or future specifications of riverscape conditions were developed, information on how Surfaces (2.7) were used or acquired, or any notes that might help with future interpretation of the DCE observations.

FIGURE 25. EXAMPLE OF A WELL WRITTEN DCE DESCRIPTION THAT DESCRIBES THE SURFACES (2.7) AND DATA CAPTURE METHODS (3.2) THAT ARE BEING USED BY THE DCE.

DCE SURFACES – Most riverscape observations generated using desktop GIS software will be based on one or more Surface raster datasets. See section 2.7 above for a more complete description of Surfaces, their attributes, and application within QRIS projects.

FIGURE 26. QRIS INTERFACE FOR ADDING ONE OR MORE AVAILABLE METHODS TO A DCE. YOUR CHOICE OF WHICH DATA CAPTURE METHODS TO EMPLOY ON YOUR PROJECT SHOULD BE LINKED TO YOUR PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND RECOVERY GOALS.

3.2 Data Capture Methods

Data Capture Methods provide a set of standard survey and assessment protocols for capturing the current extent, abundance, distribution and characteristics of riverscape features. The observations captured by these standard methods also provide the information needed to calculate a standard set of summary metrics that are used to infer the status and track riverscape health over time. Each DCE can be made up of 1 or more methods. Surveys and assessments can be implemented from within QRiS utilizing raster Surfaces (2.7) or during field visits and field survey data collection campaigns. Most projects will not utilize the complete list of survey and assessment methods (Table 1). Rather, your choice of which survey and assessment methods to apply should depend on the link between project objectives and indicators of riverscape recovery, and will depend on practical limitations set by your riverscape setting such as the ability to visualize riverscape features from orthoimagery.

When creating a new DCE that consists of the same Data Capture Methods as a previous DCE it is often useful to start by importing the features from the previous DCE. The features from the previous DCE can then be edited to represent and quantify observed change to riverscape features.

TABLE 1. DATA CAPTURE METHODS THAT MAKE UP THE PROTOCOL'S OBSERVATION AND ASSESSMENT MONITORING APPROACHES. ONE OR MORE DATA CAPTURE METHOD WILL BE EMPLOYED WITHIN EACH OF YOUR PROJECT'S TEMPORALLY DISCRETE DATA CAPTURE EVENTS.

<i>Data Capture Method</i>	<i>Method Type</i>	<i>Method Target</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Geometries</i>
<i>Dam Crests</i>	Assessment	Beaver Dam Building	Representation of the crest profile of natural and/or artificial dams, used to produce metrics that include dam abundance and total crest length (from Bartelt et al. 2021).	Lines
<i>BRAT Vegetation Suitability</i>	Assessment	Beaver Dam Building	Mapping and classification of vegetated areas of the valley bottom according to their suitability as forage and dam building material by beaver (from McFarland et al. 2017).	Polygons
<i>BRAT CIS</i>	Assessment	Beaver Dam Building	Implementation of the Beaver Restoration Assessment Tool Combined Inference System that uses a simple classification of channel, floodplain, and vegetative features to estimate the potential beaver dam capacity of riverscape segments.	Points, Lines
<i>SEM Cluer & Thorne</i>	Assessment	Geomorphic Condition	Classification of the riverscape according to the stream evolution model stages described by Cluer and Thorn 2014.	Polygons
<i>Recovery Potential</i>	Assessment	Recovery Potential	Mapping the extent of the valley bottom over which aquatic processes might be invoked given restoration or management changes.	Polygons
<i>Risk Potential</i>	Assessment	Risk Potential	Identification and mapping of anthropogenic features that would limit the area available for riverscape expansion (i.e., limit recovery potential)	Points, Lines, Polygons
<i>Active Channels</i>	Observation	Geomorphic Mapping - Channel	Mapping of the active channel extent and planform as primary and non-primary channels, used to generate metrics of increasing channel complexity and extent.	Lines, Polygons
<i>Channel Junctions</i>	Observation	Geomorphic Mapping - Channel	Mapping the abundance and distribution of active channel confluences and difluences. Used to generate metrics of increasing riverscape complexity as anabranching and braiding.	Points

<i>Data Capture Method</i>	<i>Method Type</i>	<i>Method Target</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Geometries</i>
<i>Geomorphic Units</i>	Observation	Geomorphic Mapping - Channel	Representation of the distribution and characteristics of geomorphic features within the active channel. Used to produce estimates of habitat complexity and quantity.	Points, Polygons
<i>Active Valley Bottom Extents</i>	Observation	Geomorphic Mapping - Floodplain	Classification and mapping the riverscape area that is part of the current active channel and floodplain; i.e., the 'active' portion of the valley bottom.	Polygons
<i>Inundation Extents</i>	Observation	Hydraulic Mapping	Mapping the distribution of simple surface-flow types such as ponded, free-flowing, and overflowing. Used to generate metrics of increasing habitat complexity, quantity, and floodplain connectivity (from Bartelt et al. 2021)	Polygons
<i>Vegetation Extents</i>	Observation	Vegetation Mapping	Classification and mapping of vegetated portions of the valley bottom where the vegetation assemblage is dominated by riparian and wetland species.	Polygons
<i>Observations</i>	Observation	Other	A flexible set of layers used to document practical, logistical, and cautionary features that are relevant to LTPBR implementation and monitoring.	Points, Lines, Polygons
<i>Structural Elements</i>	Observation	Structural Elements	Maps the distribution and characteristics of structural elements (natural and artificial woody debris jams and beaver dams).	Points, Lines, Polygons
<i>Beaver Dam Surveys</i>	Observation	Beaver Activity	A simple rapid survey of beaver dam distributions.	Points
<i>Beaver Sign Surveys</i>	Observation	Beaver Activity	A simple rapid field survey of beaver activity.	Points

3.3 Dam Crests

Crests of natural or artificial beaver dam are representative of their lateral extent (Figure 27) and are mapped to capture their significance in altering hydraulic and sediment dynamics. Mapping dam crests follows the methods established in Bartlet (2021) and is often done in conjunction with the Inundation Mapping (3.10) method. Dam Crest layers are used to calculate metrics of structural element abundance and crest length.

FIGURE 27. EXAMPLE OF DAM CREST MAPPING. DAM CRESTS REPRESENT THE LATERAL PROFILE OF NATURAL OR ARTIFICIAL BEAVER DAMS AND ARE MOST EASILY MAPPED USING HIGH-RESOLUTION IMAGERY WITHIN QGIS.

Mapping Dam Crests will often be done on a desktop GIS and using high-resolution imagery. However, one might consider mapping dam locations and attributes in the field as points using the Structural Element data capture method and using those observations to inform more detailed Dam Crest desktop mapping after your field visit.

Dam Crest Geometries

LINES – Dam crests are always surveyed as lines that represent the lateral extent of natural or artificial beaver dam crests (i.e., dam length, Figure 27).

Dam Crest Data Capture

Dam crests can be mapped in the field on a mobile GIS, but line geometries are most suited for mapping from a desktop GIS on high resolution drone or satellite imagery. It may make sense to first conduct a field survey of dam points using the Structural Elements (3.12) Data Capture Method, and then use those points as context for digitizing Dam Crests from imagery during a GIS session.

Practitioners should consider how to represent breached or blown out dams where the crest may not be continuous (Figure 28). In these cases, several lines could be used to represent the actual existing length, position, and orientation of the existing dam remnants. However, a single continuous line will provide a more accurate enumeration of dam elements within your riverscape whether built by beavers or as restoration treatments.

Dam Crest Attributes

STRUCTURE SOURCE – Classifies the origin of a dam.

NATURAL – The dam was originally constructed by beaver

ARTIFICIAL – The dam was constructed as a beaver dam analog by restoration construction crew.

UNKNOWN – It is unclear whether the dam was originally constructed by beavers or is a beaver dam analog.

DAM STATE – Describes the current state of the dam with respect to its condition and ability to alter flow hydraulics. The dam state is often related to whether the dam is currently being maintained by beaver, and whether past flow events have resulted in erosion around or under the dam or loss of materials (Figure 28).

INTACT – shows little evidence of breaching or erosion around the structure, flow is primarily spilling over and/or flowing through the structure and water surface gradients are near 0. Dams classified as being intact often show evidence of being actively maintained by beaver.

BREACHED - Some evidence of breaching as vegetative material and/or post loss, and/or erosion of the banks or streambed. Flow is concentrated near the breach, but the structure is still impounding water and reducing the water surface gradient and velocity behind the dam.

BLOWN - A large portion of the structure has been damaged and/or lost during high flows. Water surface gradient is consistent with the streambed, and velocities are also similar or greater than unimpounded channel sections.

FIGURE 28. EXAMPLES OF THE DAM STATE ATTRIBUTE OF DAM CREST FEATURES. DAM STATE DESCRIBES THE DAM WITH RESPECT TO ITS CONDITION AND ABILITY TO ALTER HYDRAULICS.

CREST TYPE – Describes whether the natural or artificial dam is being actively maintained by beaver.

ACTIVE - Structure is actively being maintained by beaver.

INACTIVE - There is evidence of past maintenance by beaver, applicable to natural dams if maintenance is not fresh (active).

CONFIDENCE - Refers to surveyor confidence that the landform being identified is indeed a beaver dam or dam analog as opposed to some debris or other feature.

HIGH, MEDIUM, LOW – Used when identifying dam features within a GIS session that utilizes low resolution imagery. A confidence of **HIGH** would indicate that the surveyor is very certain that the landform is a beaver dam.

3.4 BRAT Vegetation Suitability

The BRAT ([Beaver Restoration Assessment Tool](#)) Vegetation Suitability Data Capture Method allows delineation of riverscapes into vegetation assemblages with respect to their suitability as forage and/or dam building material for beaver. The approach is based on the vegetation suitability classification scheme developed by MacFarlane et al. (2017).

FIGURE 29. AERIAL CLASSIFICATION OF VEGETATION SUITABILITY FOR BEAVER FROM PREDOMINATELY SAGEBRUSH (UNSUITABLE) TO WILLOW AND EMERGENT AQUATIC VEGETATION (PREFERRED).

BRAT Vegetation Suitability Geometries

POLYGONS – Polygons are used to delineate the boundary of vegetation assemblages according to their use by beaver as forage or for dam building material.

BRAT Vegetation Suitability Data Capture

As is usual, polygon feature types are most easily mapped on high-resolution orthoimagery using QRiS or another GIS software. Your classification should in most cases cover the entire valley bottom (see Riverscape

project Input (2) for your project area. Field visits to ground truth your classifications, or evaluations of vegetation distributions during imagery acquisition are of course highly encouraged before GIS mapping commences. It will be difficult to map vegetation assemblages within a GIS session on small streams that also feature a dense canopy of coniferous tree species.

BRAT Vegetation Suitability Attributes

Vegetation suitability polygons contain a single attribute that ranks vegetation suitability from being 0 - Unsuitable to 4 – Preferred. These vegetation preference categories were originally adapted from LANDFIRE dataset, a nationwide 30 m Landsat satellite imagery-based landcover classification (LANDFIRE, 2014).

0 - UNSUITABLE – Baren or dominated by species assemblages that are unpalatable to beaver as forage and unsuitable for use as building material.

1 - BARELY SUITABLE – Generally upland dominated or barren areas with little suitable herbaceous or woody building material present.

2 - MODERATELY SUITABLE – Preferred deciduous species are less abundant, and the plant assemblage consists of upland and grassland species. Other suitable building material such as sagebrush are present.

3 – SUITABLE – Areas where preferred species are less abundant but other suitable building and forage are present including cattails and herbaceous riparian and wetland plants.

4 – PREFERRED – Areas with vegetative cover dominated by preferred forage and dam building species i.e., willow, aspen, alder, cottonwood and other deciduous riparian species.

3.5 SEM – Stream Evolution Model State

The Stream Evolution Model State Data Capture Method supports tracking the composition of your riverscape according to its membership within the theoretical stages of stream evolution as proposed by Cluer and Thorne (2014). Their SEM stages consider the hydrologic, hydraulic, morphological, and vegetative riverscape attributes, and hypothesize that the latter stages support higher degrees of habitat and ecosystem benefits (Figure 30). The expedition of riverscapes to latter SEM stages (i.e., Stage 0) has also emerged as a primary target for many contemporary processes – based restoration projects. The classification is used to calculate metrics that reflect the distribution (proportion) of your project area within each SEM stage (Figure 31).

FIGURE 30. CONCEPTUAL DIAGRAM HIGHLIGHTING STREAM EVOLUTION MODEL (SEM) STAGES AS PROPOSED BY CLUER AND THORNE (2014). AS NOTED BY THE AUTHORS, IT MAY TAKE DECADES FOR OR LONGER FOR A STREAM TO TRANSITION BETWEEN STAGES. IN MANY CASES, LTPBR IS MEANT TO EXPEDITE THE TIME OF RIVERSCAPES TO PROGRESS TO LATER SEM STAGES THAT FEATURE GREATER AQUATIC HABITAT QUANTITY, QUALITY, AND AQUATIC ECOSYSTEM SERVICES.

Stream Evolution Model Geometries

POLYGONS – SEM are mapped using polygons drawn to the extent of the valley bottom (riverscape) that is currently active (see Active Extents [3.9](#)).

Stream Evolution Model Data Capture

Riverscapes can be classified into SEM stages by evaluating many spatial data sources that should be imported into your project’s Surface Inputs ([2.7](#)). Examples include aerial imagery that depicts the active channel and vegetation distributions, digital elevation models of channel and valley bottom topography, and especially detrended relative elevation models that show the elevation of valley bottom surfaces relative to the active channel. Field visits to project areas should also be used to verify interpretation of hydrogeomorphic and vegetative indicators.

The scope of your delineation should consider the entire valley bottom of your project area. SEM polygons should roughly follow the area of the valley bottom considered **ACTIVE** (see Active Extent [3.9](#)). For example, the lateral extent of a section of your riverscape classified as Stage – 0 would extend from valley wall to valley wall

and include portions of the active channel and active floodplain (i.e., ‘active’ portion of the valley bottom). While the polygon representing a Stage 2 segment would be laterally limited to the channelized portion of the active channel, and exclusive of any

FIGURE 31. CLASSIFICATION OF A RIVERSCAPE INTO SEM STAGES AS DESCRIBED BY CLUER AND THORNE (2014). MANY LTPBR PROJECTS ARE MEANT TO EXPEDITE THE TRANSITION OF DEGRADED RIVERSCAPES INTO LATTER SEM STAGES THAT OFFER GREATER AQUATIC HABITAT AND ECOSYSTEM BENEFITS.

Stream Evolution Model Attributes

The SEM method contains a single attribute descriptive of the SEM stage classification from Cluer and Thorne (2014).

SEM STAGE – Classification of the riverscape into SEM stages.

STAGE 1 – SINUOUS SINGLE THREAD. Dynamically stable and laterally active channel within a floodplain complex.

STAGE 2 – CHANNELIZED. Re-sectioned land drainage, flood control, or navigation channels.

STAGE 3 – DEGRADATION / ARRESTED DEGRADATION. Incising and abandoning its floodplain. Featuring head cuts, knick points or knick zones that incise into the bed, scours away bars and riffles and removes sediments stored at bank toes. Banks stable geotechnically.

STAGE 4 – DEGRADATION AND WIDENING. Incising with unstable, retreating banks that collapse by slumping and/or rotational slips. Failed material is scoured away, and the enlarged channel becomes disconnected from its former floodplain, which becomes a terrace.

STAGE 5 – AGGRADATION AND WIDENING. Bed rising, aggrading, widening channel with unstable banks in which excess load from upstream together with slumped bank material build berms and silts bed. Banks are stabilizing and berming.

STAGE 6 – QUASI EQUILIBRIUM. Inset floodplain re-established quasi-equilibrium channel with two-stage cross-section featuring regime channel inset within larger, degraded channel. Berms stabilize as pioneer vegetation traps fine sediment, seeds and plant propagules.

STAGE 7 – Laterally Active. Channel with frequent floodplain connection develops sinuous course, is laterally active and has symmetrical cross-section promoting bar accretion at inner margins and toe scour and renewed bank retreat along outer margins of expanding/migrating beds.

STAGE 8 – ANASTOMOSING META-STABLE CHANNEL NETWORK. Post-disturbance channel featuring anastomosed planform connected to a frequently inundated floodplain that supports wet woodland or grassland that is bounded by set-back terraces on one or both margins.

STAGE 0 – ANASTOMOSING WET WOODLAND OR ANASTOMOSING GRASSED WETLAND. Pre-disturbance, dynamically meta-stable network of anabranching channels and floodplain with vegetated islands supporting wet woodland or grassland.

3.6 Active Channels

The active channel describes areas of the valley bottom where frequent depositional and erosional processes have resulted in lack of vegetative cover and that have substrates consistent with the channel bed. The Active Channels Data Capture Method allows mapping its area (polygons) and planform (lines) and is used to generate a diversity of metrics describing aquatic habitat quantity (e.g., total active channel area) and complexity (e.g., sinuosity, anabranching).

FIGURE 32. DELINEATION OF THE ACTIVE CHANNEL EXTENT ALLOWS TRACKING AND VISUALIZING THE DYNAMICS OF AQUATIC HABITAT EXPANSION AND INCREASING RIVERSCAPE COMPLEXITY.

Active Channel Geometries

LINES - Lines representing either the center or thalweg of primary and non-primary channels.

POLYGONS – Polygon used to represent the area of the active channel.

Active Channel Data Capture

Most easily mapped within a desktop GIS utilizing aerial imagery where the wetted channel, channel bed, and vegetation surrounding the active channel can be visualized. Additional surface types such as raw and detrended DEMs or potentially hillshade raster surface may in some cases assist with active channel identification. Will be difficult to map using imagery alone in smaller streams that feature large amounts of riparian vegetation, that have dense canopy coverage, or that have vegetation growing in the channel.

When mapped as lines there should only be a single continuous channel thread identified as the **PRIMARY** channel. All other channel threads (anabranches) should be considered **NON-PRIMARY** (secondary) channels (see attributes below).

FIGURE 33. EXAMPLE OF THE DIFFERENCE IN MAPPING THE ACTIVE CHANNEL AS A CENTERLINE (RED) VS FOLLOWING THE CHANNEL THALWEG (BLUE).

Active Channel Attributes

Active Channel attributes apply only when mapping using the line vector geometry data type.

TYPE – Describes whether each line segment is a part of the **PRIMARY** channel or a **NON-PRIMARY** channel anabranch. There should be a single continuous **PRIMARY** channel thread within your riverscape and all other anabranch channels should be classified as **NON-PRIMARY**.

PRIMARY – The continuous channel thread that carries the largest proportion of the total surface flow.

NON – PRIMARY – Any other active channel thread. Non-primary channels are separated from the main channel by islands that are generally vegetated. Non-primary channels should not be drawn for thalwegs around bar features that are still a part of the active channel.

DESCRIPTION – Describes whether mapping is representative of the active channel centerline or thalweg ([Figure 33](#)). Each active channel anabranch should contain only a single channel centerline or thalweg.

CENTERLINE – Lines represent the approximate centerline of the active channel.

THALWEG – Lines follow the thalweg, which is generally the deepest point along a channel cross-section or point that carries the greatest amount of flow.

FIGURE 34. EXAMPLE OF MAPPING PRIMARY AND NON-PRIMARY (I.E., SECONDARY) ACTIVE CHANNEL LINES. MAPPING THE ACTIVE CHANNEL USING LINES ALLOWS QUANTIFICATION OF CHANNEL LENGTH, AND ALSO ALLOWS CALCULATION OF METRICS OF CHANNEL COMPLEXITY INCLUDING SINUOSITY AND THE RATIO OF PRIMARY TO NON-PRIMARY CHANNELS.

3.7 Channel Junctions

Channel junctions, or the confluences and diffluences of active channels, channel heads, and tributaries are conspicuous riverscape features that can be easily captured in the field or on orthoimagery. The presence of channel junctions is indicative of anabranch formation and increasing channel complexity.

FIGURE 35. CHANNEL JUNCTION MAPPING OFFERS AN ACCESSIBLE APPROACH TO DOCUMENTING THE FORMATION OF ANABRANCHES WITHIN YOUR RIVERSCAPE. THE METHOD CAN BE IMPLEMENTED EITHER WITHIN GIS SOFTWARE OR DURING FIELD SURVEYS.

Channel Junction Geometries

POINTS – The location of channel junction features is represented by points.

Channel Junction Data Capture

On streams with low vegetative canopy cover channel junctions can be effectively identified on orthoimagery and mapped using GIS software. High resolution elevation models (DEMs) can also provide evidence of active channel or channel head formation. Channel junction points are also a feature that can be effectively mapped in the field.

Like Active Channel mapping (see above) Channel Junctions are mapped for channel anabranching around vegetated islands and not for thalwegs confluences and diffluences occurring around bar features.

Channel Junction Attributes

TYPE – Channel junction Type describes if the feature is representative of a diffluence (channel separation) or several different types of channel confluences.

DIFFLUENCE – Location where an active, non-primary channel splits away (diverges) from the primary channel or another non-primary channel. Diffluences are the upstream end of any non-primary active channel.

CONFLUENCE (ANABRANCH) – Approximate location where an active non-primary channel reenters the primary channel or another non-primary channel. Confluences are the downstream end of any non-primary active channel.

CONFLUENCE (TRIBUTARY) – Location where a tributary enters an active channel.

CHANNEL HEAD – Channel heads are one mechanism in which new anabranches are created. Channel heads are distinguished as the most upstream point at which flow becomes concentrated between definable banks. The downstream point in which the anabranch channel meets the main channel should be marked as a channel head confluence.

3.8 Geomorphic Units

In-channel geomorphic units are delineated within the active channel extent. The geomorphic unit classification scheme is based the multi-tiered fluvial taxonomy developed by Wheaton et al. (2015). The tier-2 classification of in-channel units recognizes 8-unit types differentiated according to their lateral and longitudinal shape and orientation (Table 2, Figure 36).

Typically, all geomorphic units should be delineated (i.e., surveyed) if they have a channel length greater than half of an average active channel width. However, geomorphic units that do not meet this size criteria can and should be delineated when they are representative of significant habitat features or provide evidence of geomorphic processes. Similarly, exceptions to the size criteria should also be made within small stream systems and non-primary channels.

FIGURE 36. BED TOPOGRAPHY (SHAPE) OF IN-CHANNEL GEOMORPHIC UNIT TYPES ADAPTED FROM WHEATON ET AL. 2015.

Geomorphic Unit Data Capture

Geomorphic units can be effectively delineated either in the field or within a desktop GIS. On the desktop, geomorphic units can in many cases be effectively delineated from orthoimagery. However, high-resolution channel topography can also be used to inform the delineation. In the field, geomorphic units are most often marked as points.

You might consider only surveying geomorphic unit types that would serve as direct indicators of project effectiveness. For example, if a project objective is to create more pool habitat you might only survey pool units. This can greatly increase the speed of your field or desktop surveys.

Geomorphic Unit Geometries

POINTS – Usually marking the downstream extent of individual geomorphic units. Points are generally used to represent geomorphic units observed during field surveys. However, points can be used within a desktop survey to substantially reduce time requirements. Optional attributes of unit length, width, and depth allow approximation of unit area and volume from point observations.

POLYGONS – Polygons are most often used in geomorphic unit delineations being implemented as part of a desktop GIS survey and provide a complete representation of the collection of geomorphic forms that make up the active channel.

In some cases, a field survey of unit points can provide the context to guide a more thorough desktop GIS delineation of unit area (polygons) that relies on orthoimagery.

FIGURE 37. A MOSAIC OF GEOMORPHIC UNIT POLYGONS WITHIN A HIGHLY COMPLEX SECTION OF CHANNEL. GEOMORPHIC UNITS CAN ALSO BE MAPPED AS POINTS IN THE FIELD OR ON A DESKTOP GIS TO MINIMIZE SURVEY TIME REQUIREMENTS.

Geomorphic Unit Attributes

Attributes for Geomorphic Units include the classification of unit type and optionally unit dimensions (length, width, and depth) that can be specified when using point geometries.

UNIT TYPE – In-Channel unit type delineated according to topographic bedform and orientation within the channel.

TABLE 2. LIST OF IN-CHANNEL GEOMORPHIC UNITS, THEIR ASSOCIATED BEDFORMS, AND BRIEF DESCRIPTIONS USED IN THEIR DELINEATION.

<i>Unit Type</i>	<i>Tier 1 Type</i>	<i>Tier 2 Type</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Pool</i>	Concavity	Bowl	Pools are bowl shaped channel concavities that are laterally and longitudinally concave.
<i>Pond</i>	Concavity	Bowl	Surface water impoundment caused by a flow obstruction such as a beaver dam or woody debris jam.

<i>Chute</i>	Concavity	Trough	Laterally concave and elongate units that are typically steeper shortcuts or flow paths that dissect bar features or form on the inside of channel meanders.
<i>Riffle</i>	Convexity	Saddle	A bar that is margin attached on both sides (either to banks or other bars) with a crest that acts as a weir. They are longitudinally convex, but concave in cross section. Often formed because of deposition downstream of pool units (i.e., pool-tails).
<i>Mid Channel Bar</i>	Convexity	Mound	Lateral and longitudinal convexities formed by deposition of bed material during high stream power events. Bar features are often only partially inundated or could be completely dry during baseflow.
<i>Bank Attached Bar</i>	Convexity	Mound	Similar to mid-channel bars but attached to banks on the inside of channel meanders. Commonly referred to as ‘point bars’.
<i>Glide/Run</i>	Planar	Planar	Low-slope planar features. These sections of channel lack convex or concave shape and are neither depositional nor erosional (i.e., transport).
<i>Rapid</i>	Planar	Planar	Steeper gradient than Glide/Run, but also planar unit with higher relative roughness.

During flows that do not fill the active channel (i.e., < bankful) portions or all of some unit types will be outside the wetted channel. In these cases it may be helpful to determine whether the feature is part of the active channel (and therefore delineated) if it has a vegetated cover of less than 50%.

LENGTH – Longitudinal dimension of the geomorphic unit. May be measured the along the channel thalweg or parallel with the orientation of the channel.

WIDTH – Representative (i.e., average) width of the unit measured perpendicular to flow or the orientation of the active channel.

DEPTH – A representative (i.e., average) water surface depth, or a maximum depth for ‘bowl’ unit types.

Channel unit dimension (length, width) and generally recorded only for point geometries. They allow calculations of metrics describing unit area.

3.9 Active Valley Bottom Extents

A riverscape’s ‘Active Extent’ refers to the combined area of the valley bottom (riverscape) that would be classified as part of the current Active Channel (3.6) and active floodplain (Figure 38). With many LTPBR projects being designed to expand the area of aquatic ecosystem function, the area or proportion of a riverscape as being ‘active’ can stand as a primary indicator of restoration effectiveness.

Active Extent should follow the same lateral extent that is reflected in the delineation of SEM stages.

FIGURE 38. DELINEATION OF ACTIVE EXTENTS BEING THE COMBINED AREA OF THE VALLEY BOTTOM THAT WOULD BE CLASSIFIED AS ACTIVE CHANNEL AND ACTIVE FLOODPLAIN.

Active Extent Data Capture

The boundaries of active extent areas are most easily delineated on orthoimagery on desktop GIS software. Other Surfaces (2.7) such as DEMs can assist with active extent delineation. Field visits to ground truth imagery and desktop delineation is of course highly recommended.

This data capture method extends the delineation of the Active Channel Area method (3.6) to include the active floodplain. Identification of active floodplains remains a difficult task; however, it is recommended to include those areas of the valley bottom that show geomorphic and/or vegetative evidence of more frequent inundation or proximity to groundwater. Evidence would include more recent signs of inundation such as deposition and/or scour of alluvial material and racking of woody and other organic debris. Active floodplains also typically exhibit increased abundances of wetland and riparian vegetation.

Active Extent Geometries

POLYGONS – Polygons are used to represent the combined area of the active channel and floodplain.

Active Extent Attributes

TYPE – Simple classification of whether the polygon feature represents the inactive or active portion of the valley bottom.

ACTIVE- The combined portion of the valley bottom classified as part of the active channel and floodplain under the current geomorphic and hydrologic conditions.

INACTIVE- The portion of the valley bottom that is not part of the active channel or floodplain under current geomorphic and hydrologic conditions.

3.10 Inundation Extents

The Inundation Mapping Data Capture Method supports mapping surface flow extent and classification of surface flow types. The method is based on the Riverscape Inundation Mapping (RIM) framework developed by Bartelt (2021) which was designed to map inundation patterns in beaver impacted riverscapes. The method is used to calculate several metrics that are responsive to beaver dam building the hydraulic influence of other structural elements. The method allows the direct quantification of total wetted area, which can serve as a measure of aquatic habitat capacity for many species.

FIGURE 39. EXAMPLE OF INUNDATION MAPPING AROUND A BEAVER DAM. INUNDATION MAPPING CAN BE USED TO PRODUCE METRICS THAT ARE RELEVANT TO INCREASING AQUATIC HABITAT COMPLEXITY, FLOODPLAIN CONNECTIVITY, AND AQUATIC HABITAT CAPACITY.

Inundation Mapping Data Capture

Mapping inundation extents is most easily accomplished on aerial imagery. Inundation extents and the types of surface water flow will be heavily stage dependent, and stage should be considered when capturing imagery and when interpreting inundation data.

In some cases where the active and wetted channel are similar you might consider using your active channel (3.6) polygon as a starting point for inundation mapping.

Inundation Mapping Geometries

POLYGONS – Polygons capturing the extent and classification of surface flow types. Polygons should be mutually exclusive and cover the entire area of surface water.

Inundation Mapping Attributes

FLOW TYPE – Classification of surface flow type with relevance to patterns observed in response to structural (e.g., beaver dam, log jam) forcing.

PONDED – structurally-forced backwater ponding behind a channel-spanning structural element. Backwater may be contained within or be outside of the existing active channel.

OVERFLOW – Structurally-forced flow out of the active channel floodplain and/or otherwise exposed in channel surfaces (e.g. bars)

FREE FLOWING – Flow is contained within the contemporary active channel and is not obstructed by a channel spanning structural element (e.g., beaver dam or log jam).

3.11 Vegetation Extents

The Vegetation Extents Data Capture Method supports the mapping of vegetation assemblages in which wetland and aquatic species are dominant. The method is simply used to track changes to vegetation extent and composition within your riverscapes.

FIGURE 40. VIEW OF AREAS DOMINATED BY RIPARIAN AND WETLAND VEGETATION DIGITIZED ON AERIAL IMAGERY.

Vegetation Extents Data Capture

Vegetation is most easily mapped on aerial imagery within using desktop GIS software. It will be helpful to use field visits to support plant species identification and assemblage delineation. Additional remotely sensed data types, such as near infrared imagery may also assist with identification of riparian and wetland vegetative cover. As a rule of thumb, delineate any areas that have greater than 50% cover with wetland or riparian plant species. In very small streams it may not be necessary or possible to exclude the active or wetted channel from your vegetation extent polygons.

Vegetation Extents Geometries

POLYGONS – Polygons that represent the extent of vegetation assemblages that are dominated by wetland and aquatic species.

Vegetation Extents Attributes

Vegetation Extent features support no additional attributes, however additional information such as species composition might be added to the notes field of individual features.

3.12 Structural Elements

The Structural Elements Data capture method provides a flexible framework mapping the distribution and characteristics of structural elements throughout your riverscape. It is primarily aimed at documenting the distribution of natural and artificial beaver dams and woody debris jams; however the method can also be used to document other structure types such as vegetation mats. The observations and attributes are used to generate metrics that describe abundances of beaver dams, large woody debris jams, other structural elements, and total pieces of large woody debris within your riverscape.

FIGURE 41. QRIS INTERFACE FOR MAPPING THE DISTRIBUTION OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS. STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS CAN BE MAPPED AS POINTS, LINES, OR AS POLYGONS THAT SIGNIFY AN AREA CONTAINING MULTIPLE WOODY DEBRIS JAMS OR A COMPLEX OF BEAVER DAMS OR ARTIFICIAL BDA STRUCTURES.

Structural Element Data Capture

Structural elements can be mapped either in the field or using GIS software on spatially referenced imagery. It will be most expedient to map structural elements during field surveys as points, and polygon and line geometries will be easier to digitize on orthoimagery during desktop riverscape surveys.

The survey allows recording point and polygon features as a 'Complex' (see attributes below) where a single feature can represent multiple woody debris jams or beaver dams. This approach will be helpful and expedient in areas that have extremely high numbers of large wood aggregates or for expansive beaver complexes.

Structural Element Geometries

POINTS – Can represent a single or complex (multiple) structural elements. Points are ideal for field surveys or rapid desktop surveys of orthoimagery.

LINES – Exclusively used to capture the crest profile of individual dam structures. Analogous to those methods used in the Dam Crests Data Capture Method (3.3).

POLYGONS – Generally used to represent an area that contains many dam or jam structural elements (i.e., jam or dam complexes)

FIGURE 42. APPROXIMATION OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENT DIMENSIONS FOR A POST ASSISTED LOG STRUCTURE (PALS). STRUCTURE DIMENSIONS CAN BE USED TO DEVELOP A VARIETY OF METRICS OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENT ABUNDANCES SUCH AS TOTAL WOOD VOLUME OR SUMMARIZING THE SIZE AND HYDRAULIC INFLUENCE OF BEAVER DAMS WITHIN A COMPLEX OR PROJECT AREA.

Structural Element Attributes

TYPE – Used to describe the type (e.g., dam vs woody debris jam) of structural element, and whether each feature represents a single element or collection of structural elements.

DAM – Single structural element, created by beaver or as a restoration structure, that functions like a beaver dam.

DAM COMPLEX – A collection of dams that are being mapped as a single point or polygon. The number of dams that are being represented by the feature is expressed using the **STRUCTURE COUNT** attribute.

JAM – A single aggregate of multiple woody debris pieces, or a single large piece of woody debris.

JAM COMPLEX – A collection of jams identified by a single point or polygon feature. The number of jams that are being represented by the feature are expressed using the **STRUCTURE COUNT** attribute.

ROOT MASS – The structural element is formed by a mass of rhizomatous roots or vegetation.

OTHER STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS – Used for other structural element types, natural or constructed, that might occur within your riverscape. Examples include large boulders (that are causing structural forcing), rock dams, or rock weirs. A description of the element type can be included in the features notes.

STRUCTURE COUNT – Indicates the number of structural elements represented by a point or polygon features when using the **JAM COMPLEX** or **DAM COMPLEX** type values. Has a default of 1 structural element per feature.

LENGTH – Longest lateral dimensions of a woody debris jam, length of single piece of large woody debris, or crest length for a dam structure.

WIDTH – Width of a woody debris jam or thickness of a beaver dam or BDA. For single pieces of large wood record an average stem diameter.

HEIGHT – Vertical dimension for a woody debris jam, or crest height for a beaver dam or BDA. For single pieces of large wood record an average stem diameter

LARGE WOOD COUNT – Number of pieces of large wood in the wood accumulation or dam. Should be 1 for single pieces of large wood.

3.13 Risk Potential

Risk potential mapping is used to identify areas of the valley bottom that contain sensitive infrastructure or land uses that might be at risk to flooding or that might limit the area over which the channel can adjust geomorphically. Examples of these anthropogenic constraints include houses, roads, fields, outbuildings or other sensitive human infrastructural elements of value. Mapping these features is ultimately used to reduce the Recovery Potential (3.14) for any riverscape restoration project, where recovery potential is the area of the valley bottom that currently or that might support aquatic habitat and processes given restoration treatments or management actions.

FIGURE 43. RISK AND RECOVERY POTENTIAL MAPPING IS A KEY PART OF THE LTPBR PLANNING PROCESS AND IS USED TO COMMUNICATE AND QUANTIFY THE SPACE WITHIN THE VALLEY BOTTOM THAT IS AVAILABLE FOR EXPANSION OF AQUATIC HABITAT (RECOVERY POTENTIAL), OR WHERE SENSITIVE INFRASTRUCTURE MIGHT BE AT RISK TO FLOODING OR CHANNEL ADJUSTMENT (RISK POTENTIAL).

Risk Potential Data Capture

Most easily mapped using orthoimagery on GIS software but can also be mapped as points during field visits.

Risk Potential Geometries

Any combination of points, lines, and polygons can be used to represent anthropogenic constraints within the valley bottom. Polygons are most effective when excluding areas of the valley bottom that might otherwise be considered part of a riverscape's Recovery Potential.

POINTS – Used to represent any human infrastructure element. Ideal for noting infrastructural elements during field visits.

LINES – Used to represent the extent of linear features such as roads.

POLYGONS – Used to exclude areas of the valley bottom that might otherwise be considered part of a riverscape's Recovery Potential ([3.14](#)).

Risk Potential Attributes

Risk elements have a single attribute classifying their level of risk as being high, medium, or low. The risk classification follows procedures identified by the NRCS's conservation planning processes, and can be used to inform conversations with stakeholders regarding acceptable levels of risk and possibilities for design alternatives or risk mitigation measures (NRCS 2007).

3.14 Recovery Potential

Identifying a riverscape's Recovery Potential is another key step in the LTPBR restoration planning process (). A riverscape's recovery potential is the proportion of the valley bottom that is available to become part of the active channel and/or active floodplain (see [3.9](#)) given constraints set by land-use or human infrastructure (mapped above under [3.13](#) Risk Potential). In areas with no constraints the recovery potential is equal to the valley bottom extent.

Recovery Potential Data Capture

Recovery potential can be conservatively identified by mapping the valley bottom extent, mapping anthropogenic features and land uses (Risks [3.13](#)) and seeing what is left. If there is a gap between recovery potential and what is currently active (i.e. inactive floodplains and/or channel within the recovery potential area), this is the space that represents a restoration opportunity.

Recovery Potential Geometries

POLYGONS – Polygons representing the proportion of the valley bottom that is available to become part of the active channel and/or active floodplain. In riverscapes with no constraints the recovery potential equals the valley bottom extent.

Recovery Potential Attributes

Recovery Potential polygons have no additional attributes.

Planning Data Capture Events depict historic, current, and/or future riverscape conditions

FIGURE 44. THE QRIS SOFTWARE ALLOWS SPECIFICATION OF DATA CAPTURE EVENTS INTO PLANNING ‘CONTAINERS’ THAT ARE USED TO DEPICT HISTORIC, CONTEMPORARY, AND POTENTIAL FUTURE RIVERSCAPE CONDITIONS THAT MIGHT RESULT FROM A SPECIFIC RESTORATION DESIGN OR MANAGEMENT SCENARIO.

3.15 Restoration Planning with Data Capture Events

The QRIS software contains a flexible construct for using Data Capture Events to support the restoration planning process (see [Chapter 3](#) in Wheaton et al. 2019). The approach relies on specification of planning DCEs that depict historic, contemporary, and hypothetical future riverscape conditions ([Figure 44](#)). Planning Data Capture Events can contain any of the Data Capture Methods ([3.2](#)) and should be used to develop and display reasonable and realistic expectations for indicators of restoration effectiveness that might result from a specific LTPBR design or management scenario ([Figure 45](#)).

FIGURE 45. A SERIES OF DATA CAPTURE EVENTS USED TO COMMUNICATE POTENTIAL RESTORATION OUTCOMES AS PART OF THE RESTORATION PLANNING PROCESS. IN THIS CASE, THE DATA CAPTURE EVENTS SHOW THE CONTEMPORARY AS WELL AS TWO HYPOTHETICAL FUTURE OUTCOMES FOR THE ACTIVE VALLEY BOTTOM EXTENT (3.9) AND ACTIVE CHANNEL (3.6) EXTENT WITHIN THE VALLEY BOTTOM AT BETWEEN 1 – 4 YEARS AND 5 – 10 YEARS FOLLOWING RESTORATION IMPLEMENTATION. PLANNING DATA CAPTURE EVENTS CAN BE USED TO DEVELOP REASONABLE EXPECTATIONS FOR INDICATORS OF PROJECT EFFECTIVENESS.

4 LTPBR Designs

The LTPBR Design section of the protocol provide a core set of attributes and definitions to track the temporal and spatial distribution of structural treatments along with their hypothesized hydrogeomorphic influence. The method is meant to assist with many design related tasks including developing permit applications, directing construction crews during implementation, communicating project objectives, and supporting report preparation. Multiple designs can be used to represent different phases of a project or to communicate the wide variety of outcomes to be expected. Restoration designs convey the location, placement, and types of structures within your project area. Structures can optionally be organized into structure complexes to help direct crews and construction resources, and Zones of Influence (ZOIs) can be used to communicate hypothesized geomorphic and hydraulic process footprints.

FIGURE 46. DESIGN CREATION WITHIN THE QRIS TOOLBAR INTERFACE. DESIGNS ARE A SUB-TYPE OF DATA CAPTURE EVENTS WITH THEIR OWN SPECIFIC SET OF METHODS THAT SUPPORT PLANNING, DESIGNING, AND SURVEYING STRUCTURES AS THEY WERE CONSTRUCTED.

4.1 Basic Design Properties

The basic properties associated with LTPBR designs development, includes whether the design process occurred in the office using GIS software or in the field, the date the design was created, the planners who conceptualized the design, and the design's status as conceptual, provisional, or finalized.

FIGURE 47. BASIC PROPERTIES COMMON TO ALL DESIGNS THAT PROVIDE CONTEXT TO THE DESIGN’S CREATION AND PURPOSE.

ASSOCIATED VALLEY BOTTOM – The valley bottom polygon (2.1), used to reference the riverscape extent considered in the design.

DESIGN DATE – Date of design development or inception, which is not intended as a date of construction (better expressed in a separate As-Built Design (4.7) record). Dates can be specified using a flexible approach that allows entry at a single point in time or as a date range. A range might exist if you are creating a hypothetical future design for a later point in time that hasn't been explicitly established.

PROJECT PHASE – Implementation phase that the design is describing. Many LTPBR projects consist of multiple phases that might include a ‘pilot’, ‘phase 1’, and ‘phase 2’. The term phase is used in this protocol to mark a punctuated period of restoration implementation actions. For example, ‘phase 1’ may describe the structural treatments constructed during the first year of implementation, and ‘phase 2’ would refer to additional structural treatments constructed in a subsequent year or potentially the maintenance of phase 1 structures.

DESIGN STATUS – The design status, simply used to differentiate between designs that might be **IN PROGRESS**, **PROVISIONAL**, or the **FINAL** version of a design that will be constructed. This attribute allows any number of design iterations to be developed and reviewed for a given project or phase of implementation.

FINAL – The finalized design intended to be used in permit acquisition and distributed to crews for construction. Note that this is different to a design that was ‘actually built’, which should be documented in an As-Built Design type (4.7).

IN PROGRESS– Designates a design iteration that is in review or that has been reviewed but has not yet or may not be designated as the **FINAL** design.

DESIGNERS – Simply the person or persons that developed the LTPBR design.

DESIGN SOURCES – Describes the setting in which the design was specified.

PREVIOUS SITE VISIT – Design was developed remotely during a desktop GIS session or on the back of a napkin but informed by a previous site visit to the project area.

DESKTOP – Design was developed on a desktop personal computer using GIS software (e.g., QRIS, Google Earth, etc..) and informed through the evaluation of one or more Surfaces (2.7) or other spatial datasets.

FIELD WORK – Design was specified on-site using a mobile GIS solution or other means of information capture.

DESCRIPTION – Descriptive narrative related to the context, considerations, and constraints associated with the design. Descriptions may include but are not limited to describing project level goals and objectives, collaborating partners, and restoration implementation and/or monitoring considerations.

FIGURE 48. DESCRIPTIVE NARRATIVES DESCRIBING THE HOW AND WHY OF ANY DESIGN ITERATION PROVIDE CONTEXT FOR FUTURE INTERPRETATION AND COLLABORATION ON DESIGN RESOURCES.

BASES FOR DESIGN – Allows designation of the raster Surfaces (2.7) and Data Capture Events (3) used to inform the design development process. The Data Capture Events (3) are specified to communicate the historic, contemporary, and potential future riverscape condition that the design might be expected to realize.

FIGURE 49. DESIGN BASES ALLOW ASSOCIATION OF LTPBR DESIGNS WITH RASTER SURFACES (2.7) AND DATA CAPTURE EVENTS (3) THAT ARE A PART OF THE SAME QRIS PROJECT. WHILE EVIDENCE RASTERS ARE USED TO INFORM THE DESIGN, ASSOCIATED DATA CAPTURE EVENTS (3) ARE USED TO COMMUNICATE THE HISTORIC, CONTEMPORARY, AND POTENTIAL FUTURE RIVERSCAPE CONDITIONS THAT MIGHT BE A DESIGN OUTCOME.

4.2 Design Layers

Restoration designs are captured and communicated using a selection of standard layers that represent LTPBR project elements including structures, complexes, hypothesized zones of influence, and even logistical features like material harvest and staging areas (Figure 50).

FIGURE 50. QRIS INTERFACE FOR SPECIFICATION OF LAYERS THAT WILL BE USED TO REPRESENT LTPBR PROJECT COMPONENTS. DESIGNS CAN CONTAIN ALL OR JUST ONE LAYER DEPENDING ON THE LEVEL OF DESIGN NEEDED.

TABLE 3. LAYERS, THEIR DESCRIPTION, AND GEOMETRIES USED TO REPRESENT LTPBR DESIGN COMPONENTS.

<i>Layer</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Geometries</i>
<i>Zones of Influence</i>	Used to represent expected hydraulic or geomorphic area influenced by an individual or complex of LTPBR structures	Polygons
<i>Complexes</i>	Used to represent the approximate construction footprint for a group of structures. Complexes are ideal for communicating construction opportunities, constraints or other design information for a particular area.	Polygons
<i>Structures</i>	Representative of individual LTPBR structural treatments	Points, Lines
<i>Observations</i>	Set of generalized layers ideal for communicating project logistical, cautionary, or other relevant project information such as access roads or material harvest locations.	Points, Lines, Polygons

4.3 Structures

Structures are simply the point or line features representative of individual LTPBR structural element locations and types.

FIGURE 51. LTPBR STRUCTURE DESIGN SPECIFICATION AS REPRESENTED BY LINE AND POINT GEOMETRIES. WHILE SLIGHTLY MORE ARDUOUS TO MAP EFFICIENTLY, LINES GEOMETRY CAN BE USED TO COMMUNICATE APPROXIMATE STRUCTURE CREST DIMENSIONS, POSITIONING, OR DESIGN INTENTION FOR HYDRAULIC OR GEOMORPHIC INFLUENCE.

Structure Data Capture

Structures can be mapped either in the field or in a desktop GIS session. When designing in the field it is expedient to capture structure locations as points. Desktop GIS mapping sessions are more conducive to designing with structure lines, which can be used to indicate the orientation and approximate dimensions of individual structures.

Many LTPBR structural treatment projects are field fit at the time of implementation. It may be enough to develop designs at the complex level and then allow individual structural treatment locations and orientations to be fit during construction. The location and type of structural elements can then be surveyed and documented within your QRIS project within an AS-Built Data Capture Event (4.7).

Design Structure Geometries

POINTS – Sufficient to design most projects and ideal for field design or as-built structure capture.

LINES – Can be used to indicate structure orientation and approximate dimensions such as an approximate width of a BDA crest or intent of a PALS to direct flow at or over a bank.

Design Structure Attributes

STRUCTURE TYPE – The structure types included in this protocol represents a comprehensive but incomplete list of common LTPBR structural treatment. The list is inclusive of structure configurations that mimic beaver dams (BDAs), woody debris jams (PALS and ALS), and those that mimic rhizomatous root-mat production. Process-

based erosion control methods developed by Bill Zeedyke (Zeedyke and Clothier, 2009) are also included. The complete list of structure types currently supported within QRIS are listed in [Appendix I – LTPBR Structure Types](#).

4.4 Structure Complexes

Within an LTPBR design, complexes can be used to represent the approximate footprint of a collection of individual structures. Organizing structures according to complexes provides a means to communicate design, logistics, or restoration objectives at an intermediate spatial scale that is greater than an individual structure but smaller than a restoration reach. The concept of the structure complex is often confused with the ZOI (zone of influence). While ZOIs can be specified for structure complexes, they are used to represent the area of hydraulic or geomorphic influence rather than an approximate area for structure construction.

FIGURE 52. EXAMPLE OF HOW GROUPS OF STRUCTURES ARE PLACED INTO COMPLEX POLYGONS THAT DEPICT AN APPROXIMATE CONSTRUCTION FOOTPRINT WITHIN YOUR RIVERSCAPE. THE COMPLEX CONCEPT PROVIDES A USEFUL SCALE OF PROJECT ORGANIZATION THAT CAN BE USED FOR DEVELOPING COARSE DESIGN PLANS, ANTICIPATING MATERIAL STAGING, AND DIRECTING CONSTRUCTION CREW EFFORT.

Structure Complex Data Capture

Structure complex footprints can be mapped either in the field or within desktop GIS software on aerial imagery or other raster surface types. The scale of the complex is often practical for mapping in the field, allowing more detailed structure level designs to either be field fit during implementation or specified within desktop GIS software. In most cases, structure complexes will be most useful when their boundaries are mutually exclusive to one another (i.e., polygons do not overlap).

Structure Complex Geometries

POLYGONS – Area’s representing the construction footprint for a collection of LTPBR structures that are generally designed to work together to create or enhance fluvial processes, but are also useful for logistical considerations such as material staging, site access, or directing construction effort.

Structure Complex Attributes

NONE – Complexes do not have any additional attributes other than a narrative that might describe the complexes intent, extent, restoration goals, or implementation logistics.

FIGURE 53. COMPARING TWO ELEMENTS OF LTPBR DESIGNS. STRUCTURE COMPLEXES (LEFT) SHOW THE APPROXIMATE AREA OF CONSTRUCTION FOR A COLLECTION OF STRUCTURES THAT MIGHT SHARE SIMILAR OBJECTIVES, CONSTRAINTS, OR LOGISTICS. WHILE SIMILAR, ZONES OF INFLUENCE (ZOIs, RIGHT) SHOW EXPECTED HYDRAULIC OR GEOMORPHIC AREA THAT MAY BE INFLUENCED AS A RESULT OF THE RESTORATION DESIGN. ZOIs CAN BE SPECIFIED AT EITHER THE COMPLEX LEVEL OR FOR INDIVIDUAL STRUCTURES. UNLIKE COMPLEXES, ZOIs NEED NOT BE MUTUALLY EXCLUSIVE.

4.5 Zones of Influence

Zones of Influence(ZOI) are used to visualize and communicate hypothesized or observed areas over which a structure or complex of structures might exert hydraulic or geomorphic influence. ZOIs can be used to describe potential responses across design iterations that include different design phases and/or for different discharge stages. ZOIs can be expressed at the scale of complexes (i.e., groups of structures) or for individual structures. ZOIs are also useful for visualizing the potential for a restoration design to initiate a response that might present risks to nearby human infrastructure.

FIGURE 54. SEVERAL COMPLEX SCALE (I.E., GROUPS OF STRUCTURES) ZOIs. UNLIKE COMPLEXES, ZOI POLYGONS WILL OFTEN OVERLAP AS DIFFERENT STRUCTURE COMPLEXES ARE OFTEN DESIGNED TO WORK TOGETHER TO ENHANCE PROCESSES THAT SUPPORT BROADER RESTORATION GOALS BY INVOKING A NUMBER OF HYDRAULIC OR GEOMORPHIC PROCESSES.

Zones of Influence Data Capture

In most cases ZOIs will be drawn using desktop GIS software with imagery and other geospatial data types, such as DEMs, as evidence. Although cumbersome, approximate ZOI areas can also be mapped during field visits and is recommended for riverscapes that have dense canopy coverage that prevents visualization of valley bottom surfaces from aerial imagery. Unlike Complex polygons (4.4) ZOI polygons are not necessary mutually exclusive and will often overlap with one another.

Zones of Influence Geometries

POLYGONS - Zones of influence are always captured as polygons that approximate an expected or observed area of geomorphic or hydraulic response or process.

Zones of Influence Attributes

Zone of Influence attributes are descriptive of the ZOIs expected geomorphic or hydraulic response type (e.g., Side Channel Connection or Erode Bank) and of the flow stage the influence is specific to (e.g., Baseflow or Typical Flood).

ZOI TYPE – The ZOI types express the expected processes or outcomes for an individual or group of structures (complex). A complete list of ZOI types, as well as their assignment to the complex or individual structure scale can be found in [Appendix II – LTPBR Design Zones of Influence Types](#).

ZOI STAGE – Approximate discharge stage that the ZOIs is representative of. For example, separate polygons could be used to capture the expected area of overbank flow dispersal at **BASEFLOW** vs during a **TYPICAL FLOOD**.

BASEFLOW – Typical low-flow conditions of perennial streams occurring during mid and late summer/fall; however, flow is continuous within at least one channel throughout the area of interest.

TYPICAL FLOOD – Approximating a flood event in which flow begins to overtop banks that form the boundary of the active channel and spill onto floodplain surfaces. Also commonly referred to as the bankfull flood event with an exceedance interval of approximately 2 years.

LARGE FLOOD – Large flood event occurring infrequently and causing extensive dispersal of flow across active floodplains and potential inundation of disconnected floodplain and/or terrace surfaces.

OTHER – Another flow stage that is relevant to your project. A description of the stage and of its significance should be described in the ZOI notes attribute.

4.6 Observations

Observation layers allow mapping riverscape features that are relevant to a design but fall outside the principle LTPBR design layers (i.e., structures, complexes, etc...). Observation layers can be used to make annotations about any feature within your riverscape that presents a design opportunity, constraint, or risk that should be considered during planning, design, implementation, or monitoring of LTPBR projects.

FIGURE 55. EXAMPLE OF POINT, LINE, AND POLYGON OBSERVATIONS SHOWING LOGISTICAL, CAUTIONARY, AND OPPORTUNISTIC FEATURES AROUND A PROJECT. COMMON USES OF OBSERVATIONS LAYERS INCLUDE MARKING ACCESS ROADS FOR TRAVEL, PARKING AREAS, SENSITIVE HUMAN INFRASTRUCTURE, DANGEROUS AREAS, AND CHANNEL AND FLOODPLAIN RIVERSCAPE FEATURES THAT MIGHT BE CONSIDERED WITHIN A STRUCTURAL TREATMENT DESIGN.

Observation Data Capture

Observations can be efficiently captured in the field, especially as points, and are also easy to map in the office using GIS software and aerial imagery or other raster Surfaces (2.7) as evidence.

Observation Geometries

Observation points can be captured as points, lines, or polygons depending on the features that are being represented.

POINTS – Point geometries are ideal for marking exact or general locations for any type of riverscape feature, logistic, or other design consideration.

LINES – Ideal for marking access roads and other types of linear features.

POLYGONS – Ideal for mapping staging areas for equipment and materials, parking areas, material harvest areas, or sensitive infrastructure that should be avoided or recognized as part of an LTPBR design.

FIGURE 56. SYMBOLOGY FOR THE OBSERVATION TYPE CATEGORIES FOR POINT, LINE, AND POLYGON DATA TYPES.

Observation Attributes

OBSERVATION TYPE – Contextual classification for an observation feature.

LOGISTICS – Used to provide project annotations such as material staging locations, parking areas, camping, etc....

RIVERSCAPE FEATURE – Any riverscape feature that might be important to make note of in a design that might provide opportunities or risks. It is especially important to mark those that were observed in the field but hard to detect using aerial imagery.

DESIGN CONSIDERATION – A feature or observation that should be considered in an LTPBR design, best clarified by including notes about how the featured might be incorporated into an LTPBR design.

BUILDING MATERIALS – Ideal areas for harvesting materials to be used in structure construction.

PHOTO OBSERVATION – Photo observations made in the field.

CAUTION – Any feature that deserves caution, especially for the safety of construction or monitoring crews.

ROAD – Access roads to the construction site as well as designated routes on the riverscape where roads may not currently exist.

INFRASTRUCTURE – Any anthropogenic infrastructure in the riverscape that is important to be aware of or that might be at risk.

OTHER – Other features that may be relevant to LTPBR planning, design, or implementation.

4.7 LTPBR As-Built Surveys

Many LTPBR projects are field fit during construction, and the structures that are ultimately built may differ from what was originally specified in an LTPBR design. As-Built surveys are a sub-type of LTPBR design that are exclusively used to document the location and types of structures as they are built. While typical LTPBR designs have an array of potential layer types for communicating structure complex groupings, zones of influence, and general riverscape observations, As-Built surveys contain only structure layers. As built surveys also include an additional temporal attribute that marks the date that structure construction was completed. Beyond these differences, As-Built surveys utilize the same constructs as regular LTPBR designs, including their association with Surfaces (2.7) and Riverscapes polygons (2.1).

FIGURE 57. CREATION OF A NEW AS-BUILT SURVEY. AS BUILT SURVEYS ARE A SUB-TYPE OF LTPBR DESIGNS THAT CONTAIN ONLY STRUCTURE LAYERS AND THAT CAPTURE THE DISTRIBUTION AND TYPES OF LTPBR STRUCTURES THAT HAVE BEEN CONSTRUCTED.

5 Analyses

The preceding sections of this protocol have presented a series of constructs that are used to spatially represent riverscapes, restoration projects, and monitoring data capture. These constructs include an assortment of project Inputs (2) that describe inherent riverscape characteristics and project attributes (e.g., study or restoration designs), and Data Capture Events (3) that are used to track the distribution and characteristics of riverscape features through time. Together, these pieces of information allow calculation of standard metrics that are indicators of 'riverscape health', and that can be used to make comparisons among riverscape settings or tracked through time.

FIGURE 58. SPECIFICATION OF A NEW 'ANALYSIS' OF RIVERSCAPE DATA. ANALYSES REQUIRE AT LEAST ONE SAMPLE FRAME (2.3) AND AT LEAST ONE DATA CAPTURE EVENT THAT CONTAINS A SET OF DIGITIZED OBSERVATIONS, ASSESSMENTS, OR AN LTPBR DESIGN.

5.1 Creating and Managing Analyses

The QRIS software includes a sophisticated interface for generating and managing analyses of your riverscape project data. Analyses, consisting of the calculation of metrics and that describe your project, project area and project outcomes, can be generated for the features within your Sampling Frames (2.3) and are based on the riverscape feature observations represented within your LTPBR Designs (4) and Data Capture Events (3). To get started, any analysis in QRIS requires the following pieces of information:

5.1.1 Analysis Attributes and Specifications

DATA CAPTURE EVENT – One or more Data Capture Events (3) containing features from one or more Data Capture Methods.

SAMPLE FRAME - A Sample Frame (2.3) containing at least one feature (polygon) for which you would like to calculate riverscape metrics. The individual features (polygons) within your Sample Frames (2.3) provide the spatial extent over which metrics are calculated, and they are used in metric calculations that are scaled to area (e.g., % Ponded Flow, % Valley Bottom Active).

PROFILE – Although not a requirement, Profiles (2.4) are used to scale metric calculations to riverscape length (e.g., Pools Per Km). Profile lines used in metric calculations should follow the approximate centerline of your valley bottom.

DEM – A Digital Elevation Model (DEM) specified from your Surface Inputs. DEMs are used to calculate channel gradient using the start and endpoint of the Profile within each Sample Frame.

FIGURE 59. THE QRIS ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK ALLOWS INDIVIDUAL METRICS TO BE SPECIFIED AS A ‘METRIC’, ‘INDICATOR’, OR ‘NONE’ SO AS NOT TO BE INCLUDED IN THE ANALYSIS.

METRIC STATUS – New analyses will include the complete list of potential metrics for inclusion in your analysis. Use the metric status attribute to classify each metric’s inclusion as it relates to the project goals and objectives.

METRIC – Values that are calculated or manually specified and that are used to describe your riverscape or assess riverscape change over time.

INDICATOR – Calculated or manually entered values that are directly tied to project goals and objectives and that are descriptive of project effectiveness.

NONE – Metrics that are not applicable to the riverscape or that will not be included in the analysis specification.

5.1.2 Manually Entering Metric Values

Values for any metric can be manually entered into the main analysis management window (Figure 60). The same interface is also used to enter degrees of uncertainty surrounding manually entered or calculated metric and indicator values.

- Manually entered metric values are especially useful for Data Capture Events (3) that are a part of [Planning](#) and used to express estimated historic values or set targets for indicator values that are a part of a future riverscape condition.
- Manual entry of indicator values may also be used to communicate an estimate of current riverscape feature conditions when field or desktop monitoring data cannot be obtained for logistical or budgetary constraints.

FIGURE 60. VALUES FOR INDICATOR METRICS CAN BE MANUALLY ENTERED, WHICH IS ESPECIALLY USEFUL FOR DATA CAPTURE EVENTS (3) THAT ARE INTENDED TO REPRESENT EXPECTED FUTURE OR HISTORIC RIVERSCAPE CONDITIONS.

5.1.3 Manual and Automated Metric Values

The QRIS analysis framework allows you to choose whether you want to use an automated (i.e., calculated from your riverscape data) or manually entered value to generate reports, graphs, or data exports. QRIS will graphically indicate if a manual or automated values exist for each metric and for each Sample Frame, and which value is currently flagged to be included in any reports or exports. The graphical representation for displaying and storing metric values uses a combination of blue and orange circles and squares for manually entered and automated (i.e., calculated) values (Figure 61).

Metric	Units	Value	Uncertainty	Status
Jam Density	#/m	0.01		
Dam Density	#/m	2		
Relative Flow Length	ratio	1....		
Channel Sinuosity	ratio	null		

Both manual and automated are stored. Display automated value
Display manually entered value
No manual value stored. Use the stored automated value.
Neither value is stored for this metric. Nothing displayed

FIGURE 61. THE QRIS ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK ALLOWS STORING MANUALLY ENTERED AND CALCULATED VALUES FOR EACH METRIC. THE INTERFACE USES A COMBINATION OF BLUE AND ORANGE CIRCLES AND SQUARES TO INDICATE WHICH VALUES ARE BEING STORED AND ALSO WHICH VALUES ARE CURRENTLY BEING DISPLAYED AND WILL BE USED TO CREATE REPORTS, GRAPHS, AND VALUE EXPORTS.

5.1.4 Metric Value Uncertainty

An estimate of uncertainty can be manually entered around any value as an expression of the confidence or error associated with an indicator or metric value. **UNCERTAINTY** can be expressed in several ways:

PLUS/MINUS – Uncertainty expressed as the amount greater than or less than the metric value. For example, 5 plus or minus 3 would indicate that the actual value for the metric or indicator is somewhere between 2 and 8.

PERCENT – Expresses uncertainty as a percent of the metric value. For example, entering 50% uncertainty for a value of 10 would suggest that the actual value is between 5 and 15.

MIN/MAX – Expresses uncertainty as the absolute range for the indicator or metric value.

6 Protocols in Practice

Every riverscape restoration or research project will present its own set of challenges, limitations, opportunities, and requirements for collecting, analyzing, and communicating riverscape information. This protocol and accompanying QRIS software have been designed with the flexibility to support this diversity and allow curation of information over the time horizons at which riverscapes might change or respond to restoration and management actions. Budgetary, logistical, and practical constraints will dictate which components of the protocol are applicable or even possible to be initiated on any project. A project that operates with a large budget, consists of diverse stakeholders, and features a stringent permitting environment may utilize extensively the analytical tools, design development (4), and array of Data Capture Methods (3.2) offered by this protocol. In contrast, many small restoration projects may do little more than document the location of structural treatments in an As-Built Survey (4.7).

The following case-studies demonstrate this flexibility, and are meant to provide examples of how the framework has been applied to a diverse set of riverscape restoration and management projects to help plan restoration actions and communicate restoration expectations and outcomes.

6.1 Birch Creek Beaver Translocation

The [story of Birch Creek](#), a tributary of the Middle Beaver River in southern Idaho provides an example of how small efforts to restore missing riverscape processes, like the dam building of beaver, are capable of sustaining a healthy riverscape over the long-term. The project is also a great example of how simple field monitoring can be used to efficiently and economically track indicators of project effectiveness. The goal of the project was to introduce and reestablish resident beaver populations within a riverscape that historically supported extensive beaver colonies. The hope for the project was that establishment of beaver colonies would increase the residence time of water within the system and ideally restore the abundance and duration of surface flow in Birch Creek during summer.

WITH BEAVER LONG-SINCE REMOVED, BIRCH CREEK SPENT DECADES REDUCED TO A STRUCTURALLY STARTED EPHEMERAL STREAM. WITH BEAVER REINTRODUCTION AND STRUCTURAL TREATMENT IMPLEMENTATION, LARGE BEAVER DAMS AND ESTABLISHED DAM COMPLEXES ARE NOW COMMON THROUGHOUT THE PROJECT AREA ON BIRCH CREEK, AND THE STREAM EXHIBITS PERENNIAL SURFACE FLOW ONCE AGAIN.

6.1.1 Birch Creek – Protocol Opportunities and Constraints

The Birch Creek project features a dense canopy cover of mature vegetation that prevents easily viewing the valley bottom, channel, and riverscape features from imagery captured by satellite or consumer or professional drones (see Figure 62). Because of this, many Data Capture Methods (3.2) that might be implemented using aerial imagery, such as surface flow inundation (3.10), in-channel geomorphic units (3.8), and the active channel extent or centerline, cannot be reliably mapped within the project area. Due to this difficulty, and because the project has a goal of establishing persistent beaver colonies, field surveys of structural elements (3.12) were used to monitor project effectiveness. These surveys are easily identified in the field and are a direct indicator of project outcomes and effectiveness.

FIGURE 62. OVERHEAD VIEW OF THE RIVERSCAPE WITHIN THE BIRCH CREEK PROJECT AREA ON GOOGLE EARTH IMAGERY. EXCEPT FOR ONE CLEARING AT A NOW ESTABLISHED BEAVER COMPLEX THE CHANNEL IS DIFFICULT TO SEE BECAUSE OF A FORESTED VALLEY BOTTOM. THE VALLEY BOTTOM LAYER USES THE VBET APPROXIMATION WITH A PROFILE REPRESENTING THE VALLEY BOTTOM CENTERLINE DRAWN BY HAND.

6.1.2 Birch Creek – Project Elements, Actions, and Outcomes

Restoration actions on Birch Creek began in 2014 with the construction of 4 BDA structures intended to provide cover for beaver translocation into the project area in 2015. The next several years saw construction of approximately 22 additional BDA structures and release of another 5 beavers within the project area. Project effectiveness was then monitored within the project area by conducting semi-annual field census surveys of beaver dam distributions. Monitoring through 2022 showed how simple field surveys of beaver dams provided a compelling account of the project success through monitoring a single indicator.

TABLE 4. OVERVIEW OF HOW DIFFERENT BIRCH CREEK RESTORATION AND MONITORING COMPONENTS ARE REPRESENTED WITHIN THIS PROTOCOLS IMPLEMENTATION AND MONITORING FRAMEWORK.

<i>Protocol and Project Element</i>	<i>Source</i>	<i>Description and Application</i>
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<i>Area of Interest</i>	Mapped by hand	Simple AOI approximated to the extent of land ownership. Used primarily to clip any additional context layers imported into the project
<i>Riverscape</i>	VBET	VBET model output, in this case at 10 m resolution. Used to define lateral project extent.
<i>Sample Frames</i>	VBET Valley Bottom	Single Sample Frame feature using the promoted Riverscape feature area
<i>Data Capture Events</i>	Field surveys of structural elements	Field surveys of structural element distributions. Only natural and artificial dam surveys (i.e., no surveys of wood or wood jams.) in 2014, 2016, 2017, and 2022.
<i>LTPBR Designs</i>	As-Built field surveys	Field surveys of artificial structure locations following each phase of construction.
<i>Indicators of Effectiveness</i>	Dam Abundances	Dam abundance within the project area showing evidence of sustained beaver colony establishment.

FIGURE 63. MAPPING THE DISTRIBUTION OF ARTIFICIAL AND NATURAL DAMS WITHIN THE PROJECT AREA PROVIDES A CLEAR INDICATION THAT BEAVER TRANSLOCATION AND BDA IMPLEMENTATION WERE SUCCESSFUL IN MEETING PROJECT GOALS OF ESTABLISHING PERSISTENT BEAVER COLONIES WITHIN THEN PROJECT AREA ON BIRCH CREEK.

FIGURE 64. NUMBER OF BDAs BUILT AS DOCUMENTED BY AS-BUILT (4.7) SURVEYS, AND NUMBER OF NATURAL BEAVER DAMS AS DOCUMENTED BY DATA CAPTURE EVENTS (3) FOR THE BIRCH CREEK BEAVER TRANSLOCATION PROJECT. IT IS EASY TO SEE THAT ALTHOUGH NO NEW STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS WERE IMPLEMENTED PAST 2017 THE NUMBER OF DAMS CONTINUES TO GROW AS BEAVER COLONIES BECAME ESTABLISHED WITHIN THE PROJECT AREA.

6.2 Willow Springs Salmonid Habitat Restoration

A contrasting example protocol application is found on a structural treatment project on central Oregon’s Whychus Creek within the Willow Springs Preserve. This project has restoration goals of accelerating riverscape recovery toward a stage-0 condition while also increasing threatened salmonid habitat quantity and complexity and expanding the area and abundance of riparian and wetland vegetation within the valley bottom.

FIGURE 65. THE WILLOW SPRINGS PRESERVE ON WHYCHUS CREEK IN CENTRAL OR. THE RESTORATION PROJECT IS FOCUSED ON USING STRUCTURAL TREATMENTS TO INCREASE IN-CHANNEL HABITAT COMPLEXITY, EXPANDING RIPARIAN AND WETLAND VEGETATION, AND ACCELERATE RIVERSCAPE RECOVERY TOWARD A STAGE-0 CONDITION.

6.2.1 Willow Springs – Protocol Opportunities and Constraints

In contrast to Birch Creek (6.1), the riverscape within the Willow Springs project area lacks a dense forested canopy. Coupled with the larger active channel and small project extent of less than 1 mile, the project lends itself toward application of Data Capture Methods (3.2) that rely on mapping riverscape feature distributions using GIS software.

The project also required extensive review, collaboration, and design iterations to establish a final design, goals, and measurable objectives. This process was facilitated by development of conceptual structural treatment designs as well as historic and expected future riverscape conditions that follow the protocol's [Planning](#) components.

FIGURE 66. THE WILLOW SPRINGS RESTORATION PROJECT USES SEVERAL DESIGN, MONITORING, AND PLANNING DCEs TO ORGANIZE RIVERSCAPE INFORMATION THAT WAS USED DURING EACH PHASE OF THE PROJECT.

6.2.2 Willow Springs – Project Elements, Actions, and Outcomes

The Willow Springs restoration design development in 2019 with initial aerial imagery acquisition and visits to the project area to assess riverscape conditions (Table 5, Figure 63). Orthoimagery and field observations were used to develop conceptual structural treatment designs that capture existing and expected future riverscape conditions. A first phase of structural treatments (i.e., Phase 1) was implemented during the Summer of 2022, and was documented using an As-Built (4.7) survey of structure types and locations. Repeat aerial imagery acquisition have been initiated for the project area, and used within monitoring DCEs to map the distribution of riverscape features for tracking indicators of effectiveness post implementation (Table 5).

FIGURE 67. EXAMPLES OF HOW RIVERSCAPE FEATURES WERE MAPPED ON REPEAT IMAGERY ACQUISITIONS OF THE PROJECT AREA. MAPPING RIVERSCAPE FEATURES USING GIS SOFTWARE IS THE PRIMARY APPROACH FOR EFFECTIVENESS MONITORING ON THIS PROJECT.

TABLE 5. OVERVIEW OF WILLOW SPRINGS PROJECT ELEMENTS AND HOW THEY ARE REPRESENTED WITHIN THE LTPBR IMPLEMENTATION AND MONITORING FRAMEWORK.

<i>Protocol and Project Element</i>	<i>Source</i>	<i>Description and Application</i>
<i>Riverscape</i>	Mapped by hand along the valley bottom margins using orthoimagery and LiDAR DEM and hillshade surfaces.	Incorporated into Sample Frames and used as project extent to inform the restoration design to develop expected indicator values during planning.
<i>Surfaces</i>	LiDAR DEM and hillshade, orthoimagery captured using consumer drone	Drone imagery used in monitoring Data Capture Events (3) to map the abundance and distribution of riverscape features.
<i>Sample Frames</i>	Riverscape drawn by hand	Single feature for the project area, used in calculation of indicator values expressed as a percent of the valley bottom area.
<i>Data Capture Events</i>	Planning and Monitoring DCEs	Planning DCEs to communicate expected future riverscape conditions. Monitoring DCEs correspond with orthoimagery acquired at drone flights.
<i>LTPBR Designs</i>	Conceptual designs and as-built surveys for phase 1, 2, and 3.	Conceptual designs used to communicate structure locations and zones of influence. As-built surveys documenting structure implementation
<i>Indicators of Effectiveness</i>	Mapped on orthoimagery from periodic drone acquisitions.	Structural Elements Abundance, Geomorphologic Units, Riparian Vegetation Extents, Active Channel Sinuosity and Length.

FIGURE 68. PRE AND POST STRUCTURAL TREATMENT MONITORING OUTCOMES FOR THE WILLOW SPRINGS RIVERSCAPE RESTORATION PROJECT. THE PLOTS SHOW THAT THE RESTORATION TREATMENTS RESULTED IN AN INCREASE IN BAR, POOL, AND TOTAL CHANNEL GEOMORPHIC UNITS AND ALSO WOODY DEBRIS JAMS WITHIN THE PROJECT AREA.

Monitoring outcomes for the Willow Springs restoration clearly demonstrate that the structural treatments caused an increase in channel habitat complexity as indicated by the increase in bar, pool, and total channel unit abundances (Figure 68). The Data Capture Events (3) also captured the increase in woody debris jams that is a result of wood introduced as part of the structural treatments, and also through racking of wood on LTPBR structures. Future monitoring will be used to quantify increases in other indicators such as the distribution of Stream Evolution Model states (3.5) and the extent or riparian vegetation (3.11), indicators that are slower to respond to restoration than are changes to the active channel.

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8 Appendixes

8.1 Appendix I – LTPBR Structure Types

NON-EXHAUSTIVE LIST OF LTPBR STRUCTURE TYPES THAT CAN BE SPECIFIED WITHIN ANY DESIGN. STRUCTURE TYPES INCLUDE THOSE DESIGNED TO MIMIC TYPICAL STRUCTURAL TREATMENT TYPES THAT INCLUDE BEAVER DAM ANALOGS, POST ASSISTED LOG STRUCTURES, AND RHIZOMATOUS ROOT-MAT PRODUCTION. PROCESS-BASED EROSION CONTROL METHODS DEVELOPED BY BILL ZEEDYKE (ZEEDYKE AND CLOTHIER, 2009) ARE ALSO INCLUDED.

<i>Structure Type</i>	<i>Structure Class</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>BDA</i>	Beaver Dam Analog	The general term describing a semi-permeable – channel-spanning structural element designed to mimic the form and function of a natural beaver dam.
<i>BDA - Postless</i>	Beaver Dam Analog	A BDA constructed without the use of posts driven into the streambed that would be used to add stability to vegetative fill material.
<i>BDA - Primary</i>	Beaver Dam Analog	A large BDA that is generally designed and placed to have the greatest hydrologic and geomorphic impact. ‘Primary’ comes from beaver complexes that commonly contain one or more large pond-forming dams that are surrounded by smaller secondary dams.
<i>BDA - Secondary</i>	Beaver Dam Analog	In a complex of BDA structures, secondary BDAs are often constructed downstream a Primary BDA to dispute gradient or within non-primary or overflow channels.
<i>BDA - Floodplain</i>	Beaver Dam Analog	A BDA structure constructed on floodplain surfaces, i.e., not build in an existing active channel anabranch.
<i>Postline Wicker Weave</i>	Beaver Dam Analog	A variant of a BDA in which woody branches are woven between posts in a fashion similar to wicker furniture construction. Produces a flat dam structure with a thin longitudinal profile.
<i>PALS</i>	Wood Accumulation	A post – assisted log structure, general term for a structural treatment constructed of woody debris secured in an accumulation by driving posts into the stream channel or floodplain.
<i>PALS - Bank Attached</i>	Wood Accumulation	PALS that are attached to the margin (bank) of the active channel. Generally intended to direct flow away from the attached bank and potentially encouraging bar formation and lateral erosion and/or migration of the active channel.

<i>Structure Type</i>	<i>Structure Class</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>PALS - Bank Blaster</i>	Wood Accumulation	PALS that are oriented to direct flow into a bank to enhance rates and magnitudes of bank erosion.
<i>PALS - Channel Spanning</i>	Wood Accumulation	PALS build with sufficient material to span an active channel. Generally intended to enhance channel aggradation rates and/or encourage floodplain connectivity.
<i>PALS - Constriction Jet</i>	Wood Accumulation	PALS that are constructed to direct flow into another non-erosive surface (boulder or armored bank) to enhance rates of bank or bed erosion.
<i>PALS - Left Bank Attached</i>	Wood Accumulation	A left bank attached PALS.
<i>PALS - Mid Channel</i>	Wood Accumulation	PALS built mid-channel, generally intended to enhance topographic complexity and bar formation.
<i>PALS - Rhino</i>	Wood Accumulation	A specific PALS recipe used in large streams with high stream power. The structure is built to maximize contact with the stream bed and has a narrow upstream profile extending into a thick base downstream much like the horn of a rhino.
<i>PALS - Right Bank Attached</i>	Wood Accumulation	Right bank attached PALS.
<i>PALS - Tight</i>	Wood Accumulation	A channel spanning PALS built of small woody material. Similar but more porous than a typical BDA.
<i>ALS</i>	Wood Accumulation	Assisted log structure being a placed woody debris accumulation that does not include posts.
<i>ALS - Bank Attached</i>	Wood Accumulation	ALS built extending from the bank towards the channel.
<i>ALS - Bank Blaster</i>	Wood Accumulation	An ALS oriented to enhance bank erosion.
<i>ALS - Channel Spanning</i>	Wood Accumulation	ALS built across the entire channel from bank to bank.

<i>Structure Type</i>	<i>Structure Class</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>ALS - Mid Channel</i>	Wood Accumulation	ALS built in the middle of the channel and not extending to either bank.
<i>ALS - Rhino</i>	Wood Accumulation	ALS built to the rhino structure design specification.
<i>Wood Jam</i>	Wood Accumulation	Analogous to ALS being a placed accumulation of woody material that does not include driven posts.
<i>Leaky Dam</i>	Wood Accumulation	A channel spanning accumulation of smaller woody material with a high degree of porosity.
<i>Strategic Felling</i>	Wood Accumulation	Felling of trees into the channel or floodplain.
<i>Tree Dam</i>	Wood Accumulation	A fell tree intended to act as a channel spanning dam, may have additional vegetative material, sediment, or sod additions to further decrease porosity.
<i>Tree Plug</i>	Wood Accumulation	Using a single large fell tree to create a channel spanning dam-like structure.
<i>Fell Tree</i>	Wood Accumulation	Strategic felling of a tree within a riverscape.
<i>Floodplain LWD</i>	Wood Accumulation	Placement of any large woody debris on the floodplain.
<i>Full Tree</i>	Wood Accumulation	Placement of an entire tree whether fell, grip hoisted or positioned using another means.
<i>Grip Hoist Tree</i>	Wood Accumulation	A tree that has fallen or that could be fell and then repositioned as a structural element using a grip-hoist.
<i>Bag Plugs</i>	Vegetation Production	Structural treatment that uses bags made up of organic material, usually burlap, that can be filled with sediment and placed. Bag plug structures often mimic vegetative mases that might sluff into the channel.

<i>Structure Type</i>	<i>Structure Class</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Post and Brush Plug</i>	Vegetation Production	Densely packing small vegetation around rows of posts driven into the channel to form a channel spanning dam-like structure.
<i>Sedge Plugs</i>	Vegetation Production	Cutting densely packed bricks of earth that are held together by sedges into the active channel spanning structure.
<i>One Rock Dam</i>	Zeedyk Structure	A grade control structure build with a single layer of rock designed to stabilize the bed of channel by increasing roughness.
<i>Spreaders</i>	Zeedyk Structure	A rock-lined depositional area designed to disperse channelized flow and restore sheet flow.
<i>Vanes</i>	Zeedyk Structure	An in-channel structure usually constructed of posts and designed to induce meandering and point formation.
<i>Wicker Weir</i>	Zeedyk Structure	A specific PALS recipe used in large streams with high stream power. The structure is built to maximize contact with the stream bed and has a narrow upstream profile extending into a thick base downstream much like the horn of a rhino.
<i>Zuni Bowl</i>	Zeedyk Structure	An in-channel headcut control structure composed of rock-lined step falls and plunge pools intended to arrest the progression of headcuts.
<i>Headcut Treatment</i>	Other	Any structural treatment intended to arrest headcut progression.

8.2 Appendix II – LTPBR Design Zones of Influence Types

ZONE OF INFLUENCE (SEE 4.5) TYPES THAT ARE USED IN LTPBR DESIGNS (4) TO REPRESENT AND COMMUNICATE THE EXPECTED OUTCOME OR FUNCTION OF STRUCTURAL TREATMENT DESIGNS. ZOIS CAN BE SPECIFIED AT THE COMPLEX (GROUPS OF STRUCTURES) OR INDIVIDUAL STRUCTURE SCALE AND INCLUDE A AN ARRAY OF HYDRAULIC AND GEOMORPHIC PROCESSES AND OUTCOMES.

<i>Specification Scale</i>	<i>Process or Processes</i>	<i>ZOI Type</i>
<i>Structure Complex Scale</i>	Composite	Increase Floodplain Connectivity
	Composite	Overbank Flow Dispersal
	Composite	Aggradation and Avulsion
	Composite	Side-Channel Connection
	Composite	Riparian and Wetland Expansion
	Composite	Facilitate Beaver Translocation
	Composite	Pond and Wetland Creation
	Composite	Accelerate Incision Recovery
	Composite	Lateral Channel Migration
	Composite	Widening and Aggradation
	Composite	Increase Channel Complexity
	Composite	Headcut Arrest
	Composite	Cover/Complexity
<i>Structure Scale</i>	Hydraulic	Eddy
	Hydraulic	Splitting Flow
	Hydraulic	Shunting Flow
	Hydraulic	Ponding Flow
	Hydraulic	Overflow
	Hydraulic	Constriction Jet
	Hydraulic	Divergent Flow
	Geomorphic	Erode Bank
	Geomorphic	Erosion From Return Flow Headcut
	Geomorphic	Erosion from Plunge
	Geomorphic	Erosion from Convergent Jet
	Geomorphic	Erosion of Bar Edge
	Geomorphic	Deposition Overbank
	Geomorphic	Deposition of Bar
	Geomorphic	Deposition Upstream Backwater
Geomorphic	Scour Pool Formation	

8.3 Appendix III – Riverscape Metrics

STANDARD METRICS, THEIR RELIANCE ON DATA CAPTURE METHODS, AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO RIVERSCAPE HEALTH PRINCIPLES. STANDARD METRICS ARE GENERATED FROM RIVERSCAPE DESIGN AND DATA CAPTURE METHODS. RIVERSCAPE METRICS ARE GENERATED AS PART OF ANALYSES (5) FOR EACH FEATURE IN THE SPECIFIED SAMPLING FRAME (2.3).

<i>Riverscape Health Principle</i>	<i>Index</i>	<i>Required Data Capture Methods</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Principle 1 - Streams Need Space</i>	Proportion of Active Valley Bottom	Active Extents	Proportion of each sampling frame classified as "Active", referring to being a part of the active channel and/or active floodplain. Sampling frames features should be representative of the valley bottom (riverscape).
	<i>Principle 2 - Structure Forces Complexity and Builds Resilience</i>	Jam Density	Structural Elements (points, lines, polygons)
	Dam Density	Structural Elements (points, lines, polygons)	Total 'dam' structural element types per length of riverscape.
	Number of Active Channels	Active Channel Lines	Count of non-primary active channel line segments.
	Primary Channel Length	Active Channel Lines	Total length of the 'Primary' active channel thread.
	Relative Flow Length	Active Channels	Sum of active channel line lengths.
	Pool Density	Geomorphic Unit Points and Polygons	The total count of channel geomorphic unit types classified as 'Bowl' per length of riverscape.
	Riffle Density	Geomorphic Unit Points and Polygons	The total count of channel geomorphic unit types classified as 'Saddle' per length of riverscape.

<i>Riverscape Health Principle</i>	<i>Index</i>	<i>Required Data Capture Methods</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>Principle 3 - Inefficiency is Healthy</i>	Bar Density	Geomorphic Unit Points and Polygons	The total count of channel geomorphic unit types classified as 'Mound' per length of riverscape.
	Confluence Density	Channel Junctions Points	Total count of 'Confluence' junctions per length of riverscape
	Diffluence Density	Channel Junctions Points	Total count of 'Diffluence' junctions per length of riverscape
	Floodplain Channel Head Density	Channel Junctions Points	Total count of 'Channel Head' junctions per length of riverscape
	Channel Sinuosity	Active Channels	Ratio of the total length of active channels (Primary and Non-primary) to riverscape length
	% Inundated	Inundation Mapping	Proportion of each sampling frame feature area with surface flow mapped as any type (Free Flowing, Overflow, Poned)
	% Free Flowing	Inundation Mapping	Proportion of each sampling frame feature area with surface flow mapped as Free Flowing
	% Overflow	Inundation Mapping	Proportion of each sampling frame feature area with surface flow mapped as Overflow
	% Poned	Inundation Mapping	Proportion of each sampling frame feature area with surface flow mapped as Poned
	% Riparian Vegetation	Vegetation Extents	Proportion of each sampling frame feature area mapped as riparian vegetation

